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D6.1 Col Configuration Synthesis Report

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Abbreviations

APTS	Advanced Public Transportation System
ATIS	Advanced Traveler Information Systems
ATMS	Advanced Traffic Management System
ATPS	Advanced Transportation Pricing System
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Consumer
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CMS	Content Management System
Col	Community (Communities) of Interest
CS	Case Study
CSL	Case Study Leader
CSS3	Cascading Style Sheets level 3
CVS	Cooperative Vehicle System
DoW	Description of Work
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
H2020	Horizon 2020 Program of the European Commission
HTML	HyperText Mark-up Language
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
JS	Java Script
KPA(s)	Key Performance Area(s)
NGOs	Non-Governmental Organisations
NNP	NEWBITS Network Platform
PPP	Public Private Partnership

D6.1 Col Configuration Synthesis Report

R&D	Research and development
SAB	Stakeholders Advisory Board
SNA	Social Network Analysis
VNA	Value Network Analysis
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Abstract

The concept of Communities of Interest (Col) is used in a variety of landscapes to describe an agglomeration of entities that can be of any type of organization or people that are concerned with the exchange of information in some subject area or that share a common goal or environment. In the landscape of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS), important actors include enterprises, academia, policy makers, associations, consultancies, and, of course, the public as end users.

This deliverable presents in detail all the appropriate actions integrated to an innovative approach for setting up Col in the ITS field. In the case of the NEWBITS project this Col is structured around four specific cases that have been defined in the project proposal and analysed in the NEWBITS implementation. The case studies act as examples of good practice and bases for gathering relevant stakeholders. In this deliverable, the four cases of Col, focused on particular sub-fields or activities such as traffic management, water-based transport of goods and railway safety, are examined. The creation of these Communities, according to the proposed approach, should follow a structured process with clearly defined incentives and processes for ensuring their goals.

Executive summary

The overall objective of the NEWBITS project is to provide with a deep understanding of the changing conditions and dynamics that affect and/or influence C-ITS innovations. The work that has already been implemented during: i) the execution of the mapping of C-ITS context (WP2); ii) the performed holistic intelligence process that included a market research analysis and a conjoint analysis (WP3) and iv) the analysis of innovative business models (WP4), identified and justified the benefits of a network-oriented value creation approach. By the application of a business ecosystem approach for ITS/C-ITS which acknowledges the context of economics of networks a higher conceptual level than the one of individual organisations is introduced, focusing at how organisations create value within the context of the networks in which they interoperate.

NEWBITS has proposed to configure Communities of Interest to foster a fully integrated network approach to the business modelling and develop a web-based network platform to support the project approach. Communities are fundamentally organized by collaborative practices, and their participants build up social capital via contributions, interaction and trust. The sense of ‘belonging’ to a determined business ecosystem is critical in activating communities. Online communities have to be created and sustained on solid ground on the basis of mission and goals, areas of collaboration established through the NEWBITS project, and specific feedback and interaction required in the diverse business network implementation steps. Apart from this initial framework, communities are structured to initiate and engage the members with regular frequency.

This report aims to set the key elements for the implementation of the proposed network business model for the deployment and market adoption of innovative ITS/C-ITS solutions. The operation of the communities is supported by the developed NEWBITS Network Platform in Task 6.2 of the project.

The deliverable incorporates an approach that advocates the functioning of Col in three different tiers, from an “internal” one that includes only the Col organizers and administrators to an “external” one that is open to the public. The key role of Col is to support a more intensive and productive interaction between ITS stakeholders, which in turn can facilitate and accelerate the application of ITS solutions in practice and advance the field forward. The task of NEWBITS Col configuration has been performed in two subtasks 6.1.1 Mapping of actors and 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Col.

Deliverable 6.1 is structured in the following sections: 1) Introduction to the Communities of Interest that includes a theoretical justification of the Col; 2) The mapping of actors, in which the support of NEWBITS partners provided a clear understanding of to whom exactly the proposed communities on ITS / C-ITS refer to Col; and finally, the 3) Description of all the proposed procedures for the creation and operation of the Col. Integral parts of Deliverable 6.1 are the four appendices that include all the data used.

organizations that are concerned with the exchange of information in some subject area (Renner, 2001, p.4) or that share a common goal or environment (Aiello et al., 2005).

Using the above definition, it seems that the Col is a broad concept that can be used for any group of actors, organizations or stakeholders operating within a given field and/or environment that exchange information and strive towards a common goal. It follows that in the field of ITS, Col can consist of stakeholders that are working - or at least communicating - with each other while striving towards the common goal of developing and establishing an intelligent transport system or promoting an innovative service / solution into market. Therefore, joining together an assortment of ITS actors and stakeholders into a Col that operates together can be an important step towards moving from ITS to Collaborative ITS, and the benefits that they entail (Piorkowski, 2010).

1.3 How are Communities of Interest different from networks?

Communities and networks can be viewed as two different aspects of social structuring which, as a result, require different forms of developmental work. In a network, the emphasis lies on the personal interactions, and connections among participants, which is viewed as a set of nodes and links, identifying information flows and helpful linkages. On the other hand, the concept of community places greater emphasis on the development of a shared identity around a topic that represents a collective intention (Wenger, Trayner & de Laat, 2011).

In practice, communities and networks are often difficult to differentiate. Very few groups have one of the above aspects so clearly pronounced that can be easily identified as “pure” communities or “pure” networks. For most groups, the two aspects are combined in various ways. A community usually involves a network of relationships, while many networks exist because participants are all committed to some kind of joint goal or venture (Wenger, Trayner & de Laat, 2011).

1.4 Taking Communities of Interest into account in the mapping task of WP6

For the purposes of the NEWBITS project, the goal of WP6 to enhance “the operation of an informal network of Communities of Interest (Col)” will apply the features and utilize the benefits of both Networks and Col. Col of stakeholders in the field of ITS will be formed and linked together in a network. The stakeholder mapping process will be used for identifying the composition of these Col as well as a basis for identifying the relations between them and their members and the flow of knowledge and information within the broader network. In this framework, “the proposed communities of interest will act as initiators to the creation of the proposed Network”, and “Col will focus on interconnecting existing synergies between them and under the umbrella of the NEWBITS project”. These objectives will take place in the context of WP6, aided by the information that will be acquired by the template and in accordance with the results from the case studies analysis and WP4. In other words, the grand goal of a network of Col is to identify and highlight the groupings of stakeholders linked together as communities governed by collective

intentions as well as the broader network consisting of these communities and the interactions and relations between them.

In practical terms, the mapping process, with the information collected via the template, will allow for the identification of groups of ITS stakeholders with common characteristics, areas of specialization and intentions. Stakeholders common features will be brought together (or the existing links between them will be strengthened) in order to form Cols that will be linked together by a common theme, whether that is their operation under a common administrative framework (e.g. national policies, interregional cooperation initiative etc.), geographical proximity or specialization in a specific sub-field of ITS. The information gathered by the template will highlight any common features that will allow the stakeholders to be linked in Cols. The Cols that will emerge from this process will then be placed in the proposed network as potential nodes. Again, the information obtained by the template will allow for the mapping of the network and network analysis, identifying and demonstrating the flow of knowledge and information between major stakeholders and/or different Cols as wholes. The formation of the network and understanding of its function and the factors connecting stakeholders and Cols with each other will allow the NEWBITS project to coordinate stakeholders and Cols in interconnecting their existing synergies under the umbrella of NEWBITS project.

1.5 Stakeholder level of engagement

The level of engagement of stakeholders within a specific project or within a network or Col refers to the process by which the projects, network or Col involves stakeholders and the extent of their involvement, irrespective of whether they support or oppose decisions, of whether they are influential or not, or of whether they are affected or not by decisions (Jeffery, 2009). As a term it is nearly synonymous with stakeholder level of interest (Newcombe, 2003), with the difference that interest does not always guarantee engagement. In this respect, while stakeholder level of engagement is impossible to be accurately assessed before the process itself is set in motion (i.e. before the project is carried out, or the network/Col is formed and its dynamics become apparent), it is possible to predict beforehand by equating it with stakeholder interest. Stakeholder interest is one of the dimensions that will be assessed by the process of stakeholder mapping using the template suggested by IntelSpace SA. The dimension of interest, along with the dimensions of attitude and power, also to be assessed by the template can be used to categorize stakeholders along certain groups which may predict their eventual level of engagement.

2 Mapping of actors

2.1 Introduction to mapping of actors

The mapping of actors has been performed according the process as is presented in Figure 2

Figure 2 The mapping exercise process flow

2.2 Existing techniques and methodologies for stakeholder mapping

Stakeholder mapping is a process with widespread employment in policymaking practice, and a critical part of any managed change initiative (Aligica, 2006). Stakeholder analyses are currently arguably more important than ever because of the increasingly interconnected nature of the world (Bryson, 2004). Managing relationships between important actors has become an essential part of any process of managing or governing (Bryson, 2004), and it would be difficult to imagine managing relationships without making careful use of stakeholder analysis, of which stakeholder mapping is an initial and critical part. The information acquired by stakeholder mapping is important for constructing a framework either during the mapping process or later during the analysis that can provide a set of specific guidelines about how the interests of those stakeholders should be addressed in a project plan, policy, program, or other action.

The initial consideration of stakeholders can be done with simple sampling processes such as brainstorming by focus groups, interviews, or referrals by other stakeholders. As the mapping process continues, however, it is commonplace to consider additional features of the stakeholders by placing them on some kind of map or grid, sometimes through the use of a number of dimensions. In the final phase of the mapping, the relationships between important stakeholders

can also be considered via a schematic representation of the stakeholder network and its features. A number of different approaches that can be useful for every step of this process have been identified through literature review and internet research. The approaches examined are the following:

1. Three-dimensional grid of power, interest and attitude
2. The power/predictability matrix
3. Rainbow diagram of influence
4. Stakeholder mapping by value hierarchies and Key Performance Areas (KPA's)
5. Stakeholder mapping based on needs and importance to others in the network
6. Typology of stakeholders based on three relationship attributes
7. The stakeholder circle
8. Focus groups
9. Semi Structured interviews
10. Snowball sampling
11. Stakeholder-led stakeholder categorization
12. Q methodology
13. Social network analysis
14. Knowledge mapping

For each one of the above approaches a common template has been used and filled in to: 1) identify the field(s) that the approach is applicable to; 2) its key features; 3) use case examples via charts; 4) if it is appropriate for the conduction of a network analysis; 5) and a preliminary assessment if the method / approach should be taken into consideration for this mapping exercise.

The templates for each approach are the following:

Three-dimensional grid of power, interest and attitude	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	A three-dimensional grid based on three dimensions which are important to know when initially considering stakeholders: Power (potential or actual influence), Interest (in the project or program) and Attitude (to the project or program). The grid produces eight different labels based on the position of stakeholders along the dimensions.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 3 Three dimensional grid of power, interest and attitude</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	Yes
Murray-Webster, R., & Simon, P. (2006). Making sense of stakeholder mapping. <i>PM World today</i> , 8(11), 1-5.	

The power/predictability matrix													
Which field is it applicable to?	Public policy / Project management / All fields												
Features / Description	Stakeholders are plotted on a two-dimensional matrix using power and predictability. The allocation of groups of stakeholders to these zones enables project managers to assess the size of the stakeholder problem they face. Different stakeholders present different challenges. For example, those with low power and high predictability are easily manageable while those with high power and low predictability are the most difficult to manage.												
Images / examples	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Predictability</p> <table style="margin: auto;"> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">High</td> <td style="text-align: center;">Low</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Low</td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> A Few problems </td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> B Unpredictable but manageable </td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Power</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">High</td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> C Powerful but predictable </td> <td style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 10px; text-align: center;"> D Greatest danger or opportunities </td> </tr> </table> </div> <p style="text-align: center; color: blue;">Figure 4 The power/predictability matrix</p>		High	Low	Low	A Few problems	B Unpredictable but manageable	Power			High	C Powerful but predictable	D Greatest danger or opportunities
	High	Low											
Low	A Few problems	B Unpredictable but manageable											
Power													
High	C Powerful but predictable	D Greatest danger or opportunities											
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No												
Is it under consideration?	No												
Newcombe, R. (2003). From client to project stakeholders: a stakeholder mapping approach. <i>Construction Management and Economics</i> , 21(8), 841-848.													

The Power/Interest matrix													
Which field is it applicable to?	Public policy / Project management / All fields												
Features / Description	A two-dimensional matrix that classifies stakeholders in relation to the power that they hold and their level of interest on the project. This allows the project manager to predict the type of relationships that he will need to establish and maintain with each type of stakeholder grouping: those that require minimal effort, those that must be kept informed, those that must be kept satisfied, and those that are key players and will require a lot of attention.												
Images / examples	<div style="text-align: center;"> <p>Level of interest</p> <table border="1" style="margin: auto;"> <tr> <td></td> <td style="text-align: center;">Low</td> <td style="text-align: center;">High</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Low</td> <td style="text-align: center;">A Minimal effort</td> <td style="text-align: center;">B Keep informed</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">Power</td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">High</td> <td style="text-align: center;">C Keep satisfied</td> <td style="text-align: center;">D Key players</td> </tr> </table> </div> <p style="text-align: center; color: blue;">Figure 5 The Power/Interest matrix</p>		Low	High	Low	A Minimal effort	B Keep informed	Power			High	C Keep satisfied	D Key players
	Low	High											
Low	A Minimal effort	B Keep informed											
Power													
High	C Keep satisfied	D Key players											
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No												
Is it under consideration?	Yes												
Newcombe, R. (2003). From client to project stakeholders: a stakeholder mapping approach. <i>Construction Management and Economics</i> , 21(8), 841-848.													

Rainbow diagram of influence	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	Once stakeholders are identified and categorized, they can be placed in a “rainbow diagram” that classifies them according to the degree they can affect and/or be affected by a problem or action: most, moderately or least.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 6 Rainbow diagram of influence</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	No
Chevalier, J. M., & Buckles, D. J. (2008). SAS2 social analysis systems: A guide to collaborative inquiry and social engagement. IDRC.	

Stakeholder mapping by value hierarchies and Key Performance Areas (KPAs)	
Which field is it applicable to?	Non-profit organizations / Perception of an organization by stakeholders
Features / Description	This mapping approach examines the view of an organization according to the views of stakeholders involved with the organization regarding its values. Mapping creates a hierarchy of values and reveals the most highly-valued key performance areas (KPAs)
Images / examples	<p>Figure 7 Stakeholder mapping by value hierarchies and Key Performance Areas</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No / Partly
Is it under consideration?	No
Fletcher, A., Guthrie, J., Steane, P., Roos, G., & Pike, S. (2003). Mapping stakeholder perceptions for a third sector organization. <i>Journal of Intellectual Capital</i> , 4(4), 505-527.	

Stakeholder mapping based on needs and importance to others in the network	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features Description /	This mapping methodology initially constructs a network to represent the stakeholder environment, then assesses the intensity of stakeholder needs, and builds a numerical model to represent the flow of value in the network. Stakeholders are ranked by their need and their relative importance to others in the network.
Images examples /	<p>Fig. 5. Simplified evaluated value network - line thickness scaled for importance of links, and colors indicate the nature of the value flow on the link.</p> <p>Figure 8 Stakeholder mapping based on needs and importance to others in the network</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	Yes
Is it under consideration?	Yes (later, during the analysis)
Cameron, B. G., Seher, T., & Crawley, E. F. (2011). Goals for space exploration based on stakeholder value network considerations. <i>Acta Astronautica</i> , 68(11), 2088-2097.	

Typology of stakeholders based on three relationship attributes	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	This approach to stakeholder identification and salience creates a typology of stakeholders based on their possession of one or more of three relationship attributes: power, legitimacy and urgency. The stakeholders' placement along these attributes can help managers decide which stakeholders require more attention, and how relevant they are.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">FIGURE 2 Stakeholder Typology: One, Two, or Three Attributes Present</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Figure 9 Typology of stakeholders based on three relationship attributes</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No / Partly
Is it under consideration?	No
<p>Mitchell, R. K., Agle, B. R., & Wood, D. J. (1997). Toward a theory of stakeholder identification and salience: Defining the principle of who and what really counts. <i>Academy of management review</i>, 22(4), 853-886.</p>	

The stakeholder circle	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	The stakeholder circle provides a useful and effective way to visualize stakeholder power and influence that may have pivotal impact on a project's success or failure. The stakeholder circle tool is developed for each project through a methodology that identifies and prioritizes key project stakeholders and then develops an engagement strategy to build and maintain robust relationships with those them.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 10 The stakeholder circle</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	Partly
Is it under consideration?	No
Bourne, L., & Walker, D. H. (2005). Visualising and mapping stakeholder influence. <i>Management decision</i> , 43(5), 649-660.	

Focus groups	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	Focus group mapping is a simple technique in which a small group of individuals with good knowledge of the field brainstorms information about stakeholders, their interests, influence and other attributes, and categorizes them.
Images / examples	
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	Yes (as an initial method)
Kretovics, M. A., & McCambridge, J. A. (1998). Determining What Employers Really Want: Conducting Regional Stakeholder Focus Groups. <i>Journal of Career Planning & Employment</i> , 58(2), 25.	

Semi Structured interviews	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	This technique uses semi structured interviews with a cross-section of stakeholders in order to check or supplement the initial data gained from focus groups. It can provide useful insight about stakeholder relationships but it is time-consuming and consensus is difficult to reach.
Images / examples	
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	Yes (as an initial method)
<p>Reed, M. S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., ... & Stringer, L. C. (2009). Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. <i>Journal of environmental management</i>, 90(5), 1933-1949.</p>	

Snowball sampling	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	With snowball sampling, individuals from a number of initially identified stakeholders are interviewed in order to identify new stakeholder categories and contacts. This is a practical and convenient method, but the resulting list of stakeholders can be biased by the social networks of the first stakeholder(s) to be interviewed.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">SNOWBALL SAMPLING</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Figure 11 Snowball sampling</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	Yes (as an initial method)
<p>Reed, M. S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., ... & Stringer, L. C. (2009). Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. <i>Journal of environmental management</i>, 90(5), 1933-1949.</p>	

Stakeholder-led stakeholder categorization	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	In this approach, stakeholders place themselves and other stakeholders into categories which they have created. The categories and placement are based on the perception of stakeholders. This method carries significant risk and subjectivity, as categories may become meaningless.
Images / examples	
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	No
Reed, M. S., Graves, A., Dandy, N., Posthumus, H., Hubacek, K., Morris, J., ... & Stringer, L. C. (2009). Who's in and why? A typology of stakeholder analysis methods for natural resource management. <i>Journal of environmental management</i> , 90(5), 1933-1949.	

Q methodology	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	Q methodology is a research method used in the social sciences to study people's viewpoint, and how they think about a topic. With this approach, stakeholders sort a number of statements according to how much they agree with them (usually on a scale from +5 to -5, as in the figure below). The analysis of these responses allow the identification of social discourses and the categorization of stakeholders in order to fit these discourses, but this method only identifies the discourses exhibited by the interviewed stakeholders instead of all possible discourses.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">-5 -4 -3 -2 -1 0 1 2 3 4 5</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Figure 12 Q methodology</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	No
Is it under consideration?	No
Cross, R. M. (2005). Exploring attitudes: the case for Q methodology. <i>Health education research</i> , 20(2), 206-213.	

Social network analysis	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	Social networks consist of actors who are tied to one another through socially meaningful relations, which can then be analyzed for structural patterns that emerge among the actors. This approach measures the relational ties between stakeholders, usually through the use of structured interview or questionnaires. It can be a time-consuming approach but it can provide valuable insight on the boundary and structure of the stakeholder network, and identify influential stakeholders and peripheral stakeholders.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 13 Social network analysis</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	Yes
Is it under consideration?	Yes (later, during the analysis)
<p>Prell, C., Hubacek, K., Quinn, C., & Reed, M. (2008). 'Who's in the network?' When stakeholders influence data analysis. <i>Systemic Practice and Action Research</i>, 21(6), 443-458.</p>	

Knowledge mapping	
Which field is it applicable to?	All fields
Features / Description	Knowledge mapping, whether in the form of a list, a database, a diagram (as in the figure below) or an actual map, is a guide for knowledge. This method is often used in conjunction with social network analysis, as in addition to relational ties between stakeholders, it identifies intellectual capital, enhance organizational learning and help anticipate impending threats or opportunities. The process can be very useful in identifying stakeholders that would work well together, although knowledge needs may still not be met due to the differences in the types of knowledge held and needed by different stakeholders.
Images / examples	<p style="text-align: center;">Figure 14 Knowledge mapping</p>
Does it conduct a network analysis?	Yes
Is it under consideration?	Yes (later, during the analysis)
Wexler, M. N. (2001). The who, what and why of knowledge mapping. <i>Journal of knowledge management</i> , 5(3), 249-264.	

2.3 Mapping guidelines

According to the Description of Work (DoW), the scope of the mapping guidelines is to guarantee that all partners, participating in this task, will follow the same approach. The mapping of the potential stakeholders is a crucial element not only for the implementation of WP6 but for the value network analysis (VNA) as well. The stakeholders / actors that will be identified and mapped will be the core of the proposed Col.

2.3.1 Definition of the methodology to be applied

Based upon the previous exercise the following methodologies have been identified that certain features of them have been used for the NEWBITS stakeholder mapping.

Methodology	Features that are going to be used
The power-interest matrix	The power-interest matrix, which classifies stakeholders in relation to the power that they hold and their level of interest on the project, will be used as a screening instrument in order to identify the key players (the stakeholders with a high/high combination of attributes), whose features and relationships will be examined in greater detail during the stakeholder analysis.
Three-dimensional grid of power, interest and attitude	The three-dimensional grid, which adds the dimension of “attitude” to the power/interest matrix, will be used as a mapping method. The additional dimension of attitude measures the extent to which stakeholders will ‘back’ (support) or ‘block’ (resist) decisions and initiatives taken in the project. Classification of stakeholders along this grid will be a first step towards a more detailed analysis and more careful selection of key stakeholders.
Focus groups	The focus group approach, in which a small group of specialized individuals with good knowledge of the field brainstorm information about stakeholders, will be used for the initial compilation of the list which will be used as a basis for the mapping process.
Semi structured interviews	The semi-structured interview approach will be used on local stakeholders, for filling out the mapping template.
Snow-ball sampling	The snow-ball sampling approach will be integrated in the mapping template, so that the existing stakeholders that have

	been elected can recommend other potentially relevant stakeholders.
Stakeholder mapping based on needs and importance to others in the network	Elements of this methodology will be taken in order to construct a network representing the stakeholder environment, stakeholder needs and the flow of value in their networks. Key stakeholders can be placed on a diagram using this approach and ranked by their needs and their relative importance to others in the network.
Social network analysis (SNA)	Social networks consist of actors who are tied to one another through socially meaningful relations. Features of this approach may be used in order to study the structural patterns and relational ties that are formed between key stakeholders. SNA is considered as a widely used methodology especially due the boom of the different Social Network Platforms. SNA is proposed to be used for the attraction of members to the proposed Cols.
Knowledge mapping	Knowledge mapping is often used in conjunction with social network analysis. Features of this approach will be used in conjunction with features of social network analysis in order to identify intellectual capital and predict impending threats of opportunities for the key stakeholders. Since one of the tasks that the proposed Cols will address is give ideas and solutions to common problems between each member's, knowledge mapping will be a key element for the design of the Cols.

2.3.2 NEWBITS mapping methodology key steps

1. Identification of actors

Each partner has identified a list of potential stakeholders. The list has not been exhaustive, and the work required has been mainly on using existing lists: previous projects; other lists; collaborates etc.

Table 1 Initial list of stakeholders / actors

Stakeholder ID	Company name	Website	Key ITS areas addressed	Case studies relation	Quadruple Helix	Personal contact	Allow to be contacted via email

							Yes / No
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	----------

2. Selection of actors to be mapped

The Power/Interest Matrix has been used for filtering the list of Step 1. The High / high combination for the actors has been chosen to be mapped.

Table 2 The Power/Interest Matrix for each stakeholder. Expansion of list (Table 1)

Stakeholder ID	Level of Interest	Level of Power	Attitude
	Low /High	Low / High	Low / High (Non Supportive / Supportive)

3. Collection of data based upon the mapping template

The participating partners in this task, have collected the above requested data based upon the following key concepts.

- The level of a stakeholder’s **interest** is defined by how likely it is to enforce its expectations on the project, to become actively involved and to participate and cooperate in an efficient way.
- The level of a stakeholder’s **power** is defined by the extent to which it has the means to get involved, to implement activities, changes and solutions that can have a meaningful impact on the sector.
- The stakeholder’s **attitude** is the extent to which stakeholders will ‘back’ (support) or ‘block’ (resist) decisions and initiatives taken in the project.

Categorization of the stakeholders on the low/high axis on each of the three attributes, as it has been expected, has been performed in a subjective, intuitive manner, without resorting to complicated systems of measurement. Taking into consideration the main scope of the use of the Power/Interest Matrix, which has been mainly to provide a filtering mechanism, it supported the identification of the actors that were mapped in detail in later stage.

2.4 The mapping template

During the implementation of the T-TRANS <http://www.ttransnetwork.eu/> EC FP7 funded project a template had been developed to acquire a common format information about each entity that wished to participate in the network that the project was constructing.

That template *was filled in by each entity and not by the project partners*. Based upon that template it has been proposed to expand it and incorporate key information elements that are required for the relevant stakeholder mapping exercise in the framework of the NEWBITS project.

2.5 Designing and deciding the mapping process

To avoid unnecessary duplication of effort and to capitalize on work already done, it was decided before hand to make use of the stakeholder database already compiled during WP2 and expand on it with the help of all the project partners. The existing database included a large list of important ITS stakeholders, with contacts provided by every partner, along with the name of the organization, its country of origin, and the name and e-mail of a contact person from each organization.

The mapping was designed and decided jointly by all project partners, with INTELSPACE directing the process, as the responsible partner for WP6. The mapping process was conceived from the start in connection to the definition of the Col concept, with the idea being that the mapping will assist in the creation of appropriate and productive Col.

The proposed mapping process was the result of a thorough examination of approaches and methodologies for stakeholder mapping (see above), and an effort to select the components of these methodologies that are more appropriate for the needs of the project, and to balance them with practical considerations. For example, after the project partners expressed some concern about the feasibility of obtaining detailed information about stakeholders without contacting them, while contacting them too early might prove detrimental for the attempt to entice stakeholders into joining the Col later, it was decided to launch a preliminary mapping, based on whatever information is available without contacting stakeholders directly and to complement that on a later stage by a full mapping.

Within the context of the NEWBITS project and its objectives, the role of the preliminary mapping is depicted in Figure 15. The preliminary mapping is expected to produce enough information to allow the formation of the Col and a more complete main mapping effort, two processes which will support each other. In turn, both of these processes will allow the network analysis to take place.

Figure 15 Important Steps of WP6, including the role of the preliminary mapping.

The main mapping, performed by all project partners, featured contacting stakeholders to confirm the existing information and to expand it by acquiring critical information for the Network Analysis, such as which other ITS organizations do stakeholders frequently work with and what types of outputs and deliverables they produce. During this stage additionally, partners had the opportunity to get better acquainted with the stakeholders that they mapped, understood and grade stakeholders' interest, power and attitude on a high/low scale, in accordance with the "Three-Dimensional Grid of Power", Interest and Attitude¹ (mentioned above), which allowed a complete and helpful mapping of stakeholders.

2.6 Scope of the preliminary mapping process

The aim of the preliminary mapping was to expand the initial information to perform a more detailed stakeholder mapping. As a first stage, it was decided that the partners would collect additional information for the stakeholders in order to assist with the mapping process. This work was conducted on an excel list. The additional information required for each stakeholder and gathered by the project partners was:

- A verification that the stakeholder organization still exists and is active on the ITS field.
- The url/web site address of the organization.
- A link to the LinkedIn profile of the organization (if any) or of the person in contact
- The location (street address) of the organization
- The type of organization according to the categories set out in the WP2 survey:
 - Industry
 - Academia
 - Policy makers

¹Murray-Webster, R., & Simon, P. (2006). Making sense of stakeholder mapping. *PM World today*, 8(11), 1-5.

- Other (please specify)
- The focused ITS area market segment of the organization according to the categories set out in the WP2 survey:
 - Advanced Traveler Information Systems (ATIS)
 - Advanced Traffic Management System (ATMS)
 - Advanced Transportation Pricing System (ATPS)
 - Advanced Public Transportation System (APTS)
 - Cooperative Vehicle System (CVS)
 - All of the above
- The target market of the organization to the categories set out in the WP2 survey:
 - Private
 - Public
 - B2B
 - Other (please specify)
- A brief profile of the stakeholder
- A brief description of the stakeholder's main ITS activities

The instructions towards the project partners for collecting this information can be found in Appendix I. The preliminary mapping process resulted in a list / pool of 168 stakeholders, with each partner providing data for a number of significant stakeholders. This list had been the basis to require clarification and expansion in the next phase, when the main mapping has been conducted. The preliminary mapping process essentially focused on a verification that listed stakeholders are still active in the ITS / C-ITS field, and on gathering key information on the stakeholders and their organizations (location, website etc.), plus the type of organization, target market, market segment, profile and activities (aligned with WP2 where possible).

Overall, the goal of the preliminary mapping process was to provide a clear overview of the profile and activities of our pool of stakeholders, and to ultimately prepare the ground for contacting stakeholders for the Col and Network, and for obtaining further information (e.g. that required for the network analysis).

2.7 Results of preliminary mapping

The results of the preliminary mapping provided an overview of the existing pool of ITS stakeholders and their characteristics. It can be considered as an overall indication of the identity of key ITS stakeholders in general, on a global level. These key characteristics are summarized below and presented in helpful graphs.

Regarding stakeholder countries of origin, the vast majority (89%) are from EU countries, with 4% based in other European countries and 7% from the rest of the world. The countries with the greatest number of ITS stakeholders were Spain (17%), Greece (13%), the UK (10%), Netherlands (9%) and Italy (7%), all of which include at least one project partner organization, plus Belgium (7%). Other EU countries contain roughly a quarter (26%) of stakeholders. The

geographical distribution of the stakeholders can also be observed in the maps in figures 16 and 17.

Figure 16 Pie chart of stakeholder country of origin.

Figure 17 Geographical mapping of stakeholders

Figure 18 Geographical mapping of stakeholders using proportional markers

Regarding stakeholder types, according to the classification followed in the WP2 survey, it seems that most stakeholders originate in the fields of academia (30%) and industry (29%). ITS associations and policy makers form slightly smaller portions of the total at 17% and 11% respectively. Consultancies also form a small percentage of the total (3%), while 10% of stakeholders belong to miscellaneous categories that could not be easily classified into the other categories, such as highways administrators, passenger associations etc.

Figure 19 Stakeholder types

Regarding the stakeholders' ITS market area segments, according to the classification followed in the WP2 survey, the most popular segment (22%) is ATMS. Next in popularity are CVS (17%), ATIS (16%), APTS (13%), and ATPS (9%), while 19% focus on all segments and a further 4% were classified as focusing on *potentially* all segments.

Figure 20 Stakeholder ITS market area segments

However, since the number of market segments in which stakeholders specialize can vary a lot, it is worth looking at the stakeholders' specialisation. Almost half of the organizations that were mapped (46%) are active in all or *potentially* all ITS market segments. Out of stakeholders that specialize in particular segments, most of them (20%) specialize in two, 17% specialize only in one segment, 10% in three segments and 7% in four out of the five segments.

Figure 21 Number of ITS segments that stakeholders specialise in.

Therefore, if only the stakeholders that specialize in a number of market segments from one to four are taken into account –therefore excluding those that cover all segments, even potentially- it is clear that the most popular segment is ATMS (28%), followed by CVS (22%), ATIS (21%), APTS (18%) and finally ATPS (11%).

Figure 22 Stakeholder ITS market area segments for stakeholders specialising in a particular segment

Regarding stakeholders' target market, according to the classification followed in the WP2 survey, the largest group (42%) targets the public market, which makes sense as the public market is a very significant buyer of large scale ITS products. A slightly smaller percentage (31%) mainly targets the private market. The groups that primarily target more specialized markets were smaller, with 14% targeting B2B, 12% targeting PPP and only 1% targeting B2C.

Figure 23 Stakeholder target market.

Finally, a word frequency analysis of stakeholder profiles and activities has revealed keywords that appear frequently in the profile and activity descriptions, which may provide some additional information regarding the identity and characteristics of the stakeholders.

Some of the keywords appearing often in stakeholders' profile are expected in light of the stakeholder's location and their involvement in ITS, such as "transport", "systems", "European", "innovation", "mobility" etc. Other terms provide hints about their identity, such as "solutions", "public", "company", "sector", "services", and of course the occurrence of the terms "research" and "development", which point out that many stakeholders originate in the field of academia or, in any case, have an active involvement in R&D processes.

Figure 24 Keyword cloud for stakeholder profiles.

Similarly, keywords appearing in the stakeholder activity descriptions provide a clear and expected indication of their main fields of activity, products etc. as can be seen by the frequent occurrence of terms such as “systems”, “projects”, “mobility”, “research”, “safety”, “information”, “vehicles” etc.

Figure 25 Keyword cloud for stakeholder activities.

2.8 Stakeholders interest-power-attitude mapping

The mapping of the stakeholder has been performed According to the methodology proposed by Murray-Webster & Simon (2006). This creates a three-dimensional grid based on three characteristics which are important to know when initially considering stakeholders: Power (potential or actual influence), Interest (in the project or program) and Attitude (to the project or program). The grid produces eight different labels based on the position of stakeholders along the dimensions. These are listed below.

Figure 26 Stakeholders categories by Murray-Webster & Simon (2006)

Definition of Labels according to methodology

Saviour: Powerful, high interest, positive attitude or alternatively influential, active, backer. They need to be paid attention to; project stakeholders should do whatever necessary to keep them on our side – pander to their needs.

Friend: Low power, high interest, positive attitude or alternatively insignificant, active, backer. They should be used as a confidant or sounding board.

Sleeping Giant: Powerful, low interest, positive attitude or alternatively influential, passive, backer. They need to be engaged in order to awaken them.

Acquaintance: Low power, low interest, positive attitude or alternatively insignificant, passive, backer. They need to be kept informed and communicated with on a 'transmit only' basis.

Irritant: Low power, high interest, negative attitude or alternatively insignificant, active, blocker. They need to be engaged so that they stop 'eating away' and then be 'put back in their box'.

Trip Wire: Low power, low interest, negative attitude or alternatively insignificant, passive, blocker. They need to be understood so we can 'watch our step' and avoid 'tripping up'

Time Bomb: Powerful, low interest, negative attitude or alternatively influential, passive, blocker. They need to be understood so they can be 'defused before the bomb goes off'.

Saboteur: Powerful, high interest, negative attitude or alternatively influential, active, blocker. They need to be engaged to disengage. We should be prepared to 'clean-up after them'.

It should be noted that the above categories are labels, used according to the methodology proposed by Murray-Webster & Simon (2006). As such, they are useful for categorizing stakeholders in a quick and convenient way, in order to prepare those concerned for what they *might* encounter, but, as labels they are generic and oversimplifying. They need to be supplemented with actual observations once the interested parties become better acquainted with the stakeholders.

This is also true in the context of the NEWBITS Col. The stakeholder mapping and resulting labels can offer the NEWBITS partners an idea of what to expect and what to watch out from each stakeholder when setting up the Col, when planning for their development and potential and when taking into account potential risks. The labels should not predispose the Col operators but they can provide a picture of the type of interaction which can be expected. Nevertheless, the results of the mapping using the Murray-Webster & Simon (2006) methodology and the fact that it has shown that a very high proportion of stakeholders have positive attitude and interest towards the topic at hand, with 52% labelled as "saviours" and 18% as "friends" (Figure 27) bodes well for the function of the Col.

Figure 27 Stakeholders' profile towards NEWBITS

Figure 28 Number of stakeholders per category

Figure 29 Categorisation of stakeholder by interest, power and attitude

2.9 Stakeholders network analysis

NEWBITS consortium partners during the stakeholders mapping exercise have provided a list of 166 persons (names and contact details) that are considered as potential members of the proposed Col. Each person is related to an organisation / enterprise / entity. One hundred fifty (150) unique organisations have been identified (See Appendix III: List of unique organisations).

According to the mapping template, the entities connected to each of the organisations identified, had to be identified as well. Connected entities are defined as commercial partners or partners to projects. In most of the organisations the connected entities have been registered as web links to pages (from each organisation's website) that display the list of their collaborating organisations. After elaborating the different lists of connected organisations via exploring the web pages, a table of 6,951 connections has been constructed.

After the mapping exercise the next implemented aim has been to understand how the identified entities / organisations are connected and form networks. This network analysis has been conducted using a modification of the methodology proposed by Prell et al. (2008). In their work they have demonstrated how knowledge gained from analysing the social networks of stakeholders can be harnessed for selecting stakeholders, and further, how this analysis can be influenced by the expressed wishes and concerns of stakeholders. The authors began their SNA using concepts derived from the resource-management literature, as we have been doing in the implementation of NEWBITS D6.1.

The analysis of the connections identified 4006 unique global entities that are associated in a way with the 150 unique organisations that represent the second level of stakeholders' connections.

Figure 30 Network analysis key figures

After the creation of the list of the 6,951 connections, INTELSPACE SA, used a social network analysis tool called NodeXL, in order to identify key components about the network. Social network analysis (SNA) is a powerful way to organize a connected world. Network analysis revealed insights into the ways that the identified entities connect with one another and form groups.

2.9.1 Network analysis

According to Wikipedia a social network is a social structure made up of a set of social actors (such as individuals or organizations), sets of dyadic ties, and other social interactions between actors. The social network perspective provides a set of methods for analyzing the structure of whole social entities as well as a variety of theories explaining the patterns observed in these structures (Wasserman, S.; Faust, K., 1994). The study of these structures uses social network analysis to identify local and global patterns, locate influential entities, and examine network dynamics.

The following table summarizes the key metrics that describe the resulted graph produced by the SNA performed with the NodeXL. The direction of the relations of the entities / organisations is not been possible to be identified hence the produced graph has been undirected. The graph displays 1905 vertices, 1896 out of which are unique edges. The total edges are 6951. Fourteen (14) connected components have been identified. A connected component is a set of vertices that are connected to each other but not to the rest of the graph.

The calculated graph density is 0.00113313. This is a ratio that compares the number of edges in the graph with the maximum number of edges the graph would have if all the vertices were

connected to each other. For the calculation of the graph density duplicate edges and self-loops are ignored. The low graph density can be interpreted as a very distributed network.

Table 3 Graph metrics of the SNA by NodeXL

Graph Metric	Value	
Graph Type	Undirected	
Vertices	1905	The number of vertices in the graph.
Unique Edges	1896	The number of edges that do not have duplicates.
Edges with Duplicates	5055	The number of edges that have duplicates.
Total Edges	6951	This is the sum of Unique Edges and Edges with Duplicates.
Connected Components	14	The number of connected components in the graph. A connected component is a set of vertices that are connected to each other but not to the rest of the graph.
Single-Vertex Connected Components	0	The number of connected components that have only one vertex.
Maximum Vertices in a Connected Component	1865	The number of vertices in the connected component that has the most vertices.
Maximum Edges in a Connected Component	6876	The number of edges in the connected component that has the most edges.
Maximum Geodesic Distance (Diameter)	8	The maximum geodesic distance among all vertex pairs, where geodesic distance is the distance between two vertices along the shortest path between them.
Average Geodesic Distance	3.874078	The average geodesic distance among all vertex pairs, where geodesic distance is the distance between two vertices along the shortest path between them.
Graph Density	0.00113313	This is a ratio that compares the number of edges in the graph with the maximum number of edges the graph would have if all the vertices were connected to each other. Duplicate edges and self-loops are ignored
NodeXL Version	1.0.1.396	

For the identification of the most important entities Table 4 orders in descending the organisations (i.e. vertices). The degree is a count of the number of connections for each node. To simplify the analysis and get value added results for the Col configuration the following filter has been applied: Vertex Degree \geq 20

Table 4 Ranking entities through number of connections

Vertex	Label of entities	Degree
ITS America	ITS America	159
IRU	International Road Transport Union (IRU)	135
Connekt/ITS Netherlands	Connekt/ITS Netherlands	126
ISINNOVA	ISINNOVA	112
UOWM	Dpt of Mechanical Engineering, Univ. of Western Macedonia	102
CO G 1824	Shenzhen Huaru Technology Co., Ltd.	101
ITS Taiwan	ITS Taiwan	88
ITS Finland	ITS Finland	82
ITS Spain	ITS Spain	78
TREDIT	TREDIT S.A	70
ITS Shenzhen	ITS Shenzhen	68
ITS Belgium	ITS Belgium	53
ITS Ireland	ITS Ireland	52
ITS Australia	ITS Australia	49
ERF	ERF (European Road Federation)	48
ITS Romania	ITS Romania	43
ITS Israel	ITS Israel	36
ITS Portugal	ITS Portugal	36
ITS Argentina	ITS Argentina	34
ITS Germany	ITS Germany	30
SEPVE	Association of Information Technology Companies of Northern Greece (SEPVE)	29
EPIKINONIA	EPIKINONIA Ltd	24
EMPHASIS	Emphasis Telematics SA	24
IQ Taxi	IQ Taxi Inc	24
ITS Sweden	ITS Sweden	24
LLA	Latvian Logistics Association	23
CTAG	CTAG - Galician Automotive Technology Centre	20
Technical University of Munich	Technical University of Munich	20

Figure 31 Fruchterman- Reingo network map

Figure 32 Harel- Koren Multiple scale network map

Figure 33 Figure 32 Harel- Koren Multiple scale network map - core detail

2.9.2 Clustering

One of the challenges in SNA is the identification of community structures in networks. The identification of communities inside the networks can be achieved by performing cluster analysis. Clustering is the task of dividing the population or data points into a number of groups such that data points in the same groups are more similar to other data points in the same group than those in other groups. Clauset, A., Newman M. E. J. and Moore C. in their research paper “Finding community structure in very large networks” presented a hierarchical agglomeration algorithm for detecting community structure faster than other algorithms. NodeXL using this algorithm graphs meaningful communities from the analyzed network, revealing large-scale patterns.

The graph was laid out using the Fruchterman-Reingold layout algorithm.

Table 5 Key identified groups / /clusters

	Number of members	Cluster key members
Vertex Group: 1	186	Connekt/ITS Netherlands; ITS Finland
Vertex Group: 2	147	ITS America
Vertex Group: 3	132	Shenzhen Huaru Texhnology Co, Ltd.
Vertex Group: 4	131	International Road Transport Union (IRU)
Vertex Group: 5	115	ITS Belgium; ITS Portugal; ITS Network

Figure 34 Major identified clusters

Figure 35 Identified Group G1: Connekt / ITS Netherlande - ITS Finland

Figure 37 Identified group G3: Shenzhen Huaru Technology Co., Ltd.

Figure 39 Identified group G5: ITS Belgium - Transport and Telecommunication Institute

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Figure 42 Identified group G8: ITS Taiwan

Figure 43 Identified group G9: ITS Ireland; ITS Germany

Figure 44 Identified group G10: ITS Spain

2.9.3 Stakeholders Network Analysis Conclusions

From the results of the stakeholder's interest-power-attitude mapping and the stakeholders network analysis the following entities /organisations are considered important based upon the number of connections that each one has and can be identified in their websites.

The following organisations are considered as valuable members for the Col that, should be contacted by Col responsible partners i.e. CSLs.

Table 6 Identified most important entities for the Col

Organization / Entity	URL
ITS America	https://www.itsa.org/
International Road Transport Union (IRU)	https://www.iru.org/
Connekt/ITS Netherlands	https://www.connekt.nl/en/
ISINNOVA	http://www.isinnova.org/
Dpt of Mechanical Engineering, Univ. of Western Macedonia	http://mech.uowm.gr/index.php/en/
Shenzhen Huaru Technology Co., Ltd.	http://www.hktdc.com/en-buyer/
ITS Taiwan	http://www.its-taiwan.org.tw/ch/index.asp
ITS Finland	http://www.its-finland.fi/index.php/en/
ITS Spain	https://www.itsspain.es/
TREDIT S.A	http://www.tredit.gr/
ITS Shenzhen	http://www.szitsa.org/ More info: https://www.yumpu.com/en/document/view/28619420/intelligent-transport-system-association-of-shenzhen-urba-2000
ITS Belgium	https://www.its.be/
ITS Ireland	https://www.itsireland.ie/
ITS Australia	https://www.its-australia.com.au/
ERF (European Road Federation)	http://erf.be/
ITS Romania	http://www.its-romania.ro/
ITS Israel	http://www.itsisrael.org/

ITS Portugal	http://www.its-portugal.com/
ITS Argentina	http://www.itsargentina.org.ar/
ITS Germany	http://www.itsgermany.org/
Association of Information Technology Companies of Northern Greece (SEPVE)	http://www.sepve.org/
EPIKINONIA Ltd	http://epi.com.gr/site/home
Emphasis Telematics SA	http://www.emphasisnet.gr/en/
IQ Taxi Inc	http://www.iqtaxi.com/iqtaxi/en/
ITS Sweden	http://its-sweden.se/
Latvian Logistics Association	http://lla.lv/en/home-2/
CTAG - Galician Automotive Technology Centre	http://ctag.com/en/
Technical University of Munich	https://www.tum.de/en/homepage/

3 Creation and Operation of the Communities of Interest

3.1 Configuration - Guidelines

To effectively configure the proposed Col, first it should be justified why potential members would participate in the NEWBITS Col. Reasoning of such an action is considered a quite complicated multi variable process. The participation in any Community of Interest has both tangible and intangible benefits. Col are considered as one form of socialization for specific scopes. There are different forms of associations or groups of interest that attempt to fulfil similar scopes as the proposed NEWBITS Col.

The members of Col would be able to get insight from leading actors such as industry associations and other stakeholders on issues related to the C-ITS issues on the four case studies. The case studies, as already being analysed in different WPs from different perspectives, target key priority areas applicable to ITS and C-ITS across Europe. Initiatives on ITS and C-ITS in Europe and elsewhere, demonstrating best practices from different points of view and how to implement similarly in a variety of circumstances, would also be included in the Col. The content created by the consortium members during the development of the NEWBITS project will be available for discussion between the Col members. The interaction with other members featuring companies and associations is one of the key benefits. These interactions are the realization of the networking opportunities between the members of the Cols.

The foreseen benefits for the potential members will be further elaborated, though according to initial feedback from the consortium: i) raising the awareness on the state of the art on the fields of (C-) ICT; and ii) the development of common initiatives (Projects EC-funded and national,

private) are considered important. Potential match-making of suppliers and customers of the C-ITS solutions / services and the potential opportunities to implement crowdfunding campaigns look promising.

The consortium has unanimously agreed that Cols configuration will be based on the four (4) case studies (CS) as proposed in the DoW.

Figure 45 NEWBITS Communities of Interest per case studies

Each one of the NEWBITS Col will include three (3) tiers. The following Figure 46 presents the scope that each tier will try to fulfil.

Figure 46 The tiers that will be included in each Col

Each tier is defined from its scope, potential members and the time frame that will operate.

Table 7 Tiers Configuration

	Title	Members	Scope	Time frame
Tier 1	Supporting internally NEWBITS	Consortium partners	Support the activities of WP3; WP4; WP5 and WP7	From the start of the project till the end of the project
Tier 2	Discussing ITS between an advanced group of ITS/C-ITS experts	Consortium partners; SAB; CS stakeholders	CS stakeholders will work towards addressing the barriers and enhance the enablers identified in WP2 in a collective way. CS stakeholders support the activities of WP3, 4, 5 and 7	From the finalization of the Col configuration till the end of the project.
Tier 3	Promoting and realising ITS/C-ITS solutions	Open to all identified stakeholders	Support the financially successful launch of C-ITS solutions through new business models	From the finalization of Case Studies analysis and the mapping of stakeholders.

3.1.1 Communities of Interest support the implementation of all NEWBITS activities

One of the aims of the proposed Col is to support the implementation of all activities that are taking place during the NEWBITS project life cycle. Consortium members can be considered that have already formed a Col since they are different entities that have been agglomerated to serve a common goal i.e. the successful implementation of NEWBITS project. As described in the GA there are specific tasks allocated to each member. These elements plus the common interest of the members on New Business Models and for some of the ITS and C-ITS justify that a COI have been formed.

3.1.1.1 WP3: Holistic Intelligence process

The scope of WP3 has been to develop and apply a holistic intelligence process that gathers relevant information at five key levels: products, market, demand, stakeholders and innovation diffusion for ITS and C-ITS. The holistic approach according to our project's proposal is based on the implementation of a market research analysis, a conjoint analysis and a benchmark analysis on the innovation diffusion of C-ITS applications in both the US and EU.

The Col will be an integral part of this holistic intelligence process focusing all the actors operating and competing in, defined through the case studies, markets or business ecosystems to maintain, expand and continually improve the results of the economic activity on a sustainable manner. Col, mainly in the defined Tier1 and Tier2, will support the partners of the consortium in order to assess the development of an efficient framework for the deployment for ITS and C-ITS. Col will support the evaluation of the current situation of the respective markets and how user preferences might shape the diverse strategies for profitable growth.

Col will support the tasks implemented during WP3 in the following ways:

- i) Support from the Col in the interaction with stakeholders

Within WP3 several interactions are foreseen with the stakeholders and rather than expect them to interact with the project based in their personal relationship with the Case Study leaders, it is proposed for them to be part of the community (Col) so they "feel" they are part of the project and not only guests included in a single Case Study.

- ii) Support from the Col in the interaction with end-users.

One of the most ambitious tasks to be implemented in WP3 is the Conjoint Analysis. Once the WPL in consultation with all the partners and stakeholders has selected the attributes and profiles, a questionnaire will be designed and required to be completed by the four (4) case studies end users. The "data gathering" activity had been proposed to be facilitated by the Col and the proposed NNP.

- iii) Benchmarking ITS innovations: EU vs US

Tier2 and Tier3 of the Col will expand the available contacts with foreign actors, sharing partnerships and/or engagements. The benchmarking exercise, performed in WP3, will reveal pitfalls in the innovation diffusion processes, potentially adding a comparative element amongst the two continents. Col tiers are concentric circles, hence members of Tier 1 will be part of Tier 3 as well. The benchmarking exercise intends to support NEWBITS Col Tier1 and Tier 2 members in the identification of relevant projects, initiatives and active actors in the ITS and C-ITS domain in the US. The task of mutual learning will be facilitated through the utilization of the NEWBITS Network Platform (NNP).

3.1.1.2 WP4: Developing Innovative Business Models

WP4 focuses on the economic and commercial aspects of (C-)ITS. These aspects will be addressed via desk research for new business models suited to (C-) ITS and a tailored approach to the Value Network Analysis (VNA). The developed VNA aims to generate a comprehensive description of where value lies in a network and how it is created. Implementing this network-based approach for the 4 C-ITS case studies, WP4 expects to provide the key to understanding the competitive environment, bringing up valuable knowledge on where value lies in a given network, how value is co-created, how the activities in the network impact the network and how the network responds to those.

The Col will support the tasks implemented through WP4 in the following ways:

Col will support the identification of highest value-producing interactions at each case study (amongst the diverse stakeholders, responding to the questionnaire designed for a quantitative analysis). The operation of Col Tier 2 will support the process in order to determine the stakeholders' preferences and to calculate the value flow scores.

Col Tier2 operations supported by intelligent functions and tools of the NNP is proposed to: i) assist online / offline data collection to categorize the intensity of each specific need of each stakeholder; ii) define the source importance; iii) help in mapping the identified networks and estimating the values of each node and connection (VNA); iv) support the value proposition crafting, and v) assist the design of business models for each of the four (4) case studies.

Tier2 of the foreseen Col, which members include: the consortium members; the SAB and the CSs stakeholders is considered as a community with activities not only taking place in the virtual / online space but in real world as well. The workshops that are foreseen to be implemented to support the value proposition crafting and the consultation process to ensure alignment of business modelling with stakeholders will be supported by the Col Tier 2 (through utilizing functions of the NNP).

3.1.1.3 WP5: NEWBITS Business case validation, guidelines and training

WP5 will formalise the understanding of the potential system benefits and fundamental economics of new business models suited to (C-) ITS in the European context reached by previous work packages. This is foreseen to lead to policy papers to inform corporate, local and regional-level decision-making as well as to provide recommendations for action in the transport development arena. The described formalisation will take the form of three (3) main outcomes: a set of guidelines for developing best practice (C-) ITS business cases; a set of recommendations on policies for enhancing C-ITS deployment across Europe and a training guide on network business modelling for C-ITS.

Col Tier1 and Tier2 will support the development of (C-) ITS business case guidelines. Col will be initiated to provide feedback on the business case guidelines proposal by WPL and brainstorm on the (C-) ITS business case template. The involvement of Tier1 and Tier2 to evaluate risk and

benefits of the new business models is another way for Col to support the formalization of (C-) ITS business case guidelines and templates.

As already mentioned, one of the scopes of WP5, is to inform corporate, local and regional-level decision-making as well as to provide recommendations for actions in the transport development arena. This awareness raising process will be initiated by Col and all the three tiers are foreseen to be involved. This process will be supported by a training programme and policy recommendations. Members of Col, Tier1 and Tier2, will be actively involved to help define the best training methods and tools.

The proposed NNP is considered to be a strategic tool in order to support this awareness raising process. Therefore, the NNP will agglomerate different online tools / applications to support forums, e-mails distribution, webinars, social media, newsletter, online tutorials; YouTube videos and others.

3.1.1.4 WP7: Communication and Dissemination

The aim of the WP7 is to increase the visibility of key project outputs and outcomes, promote the NNP and linking with relevant key initiatives. National, European technology platforms and associations and US counterparts operating directly or transversally in the ITS area, other projects in the support of (C-) ITS innovation and deployment can be invited as members of the proposed Col.

A Col is considered as one of the most important elements for the successful implementation of the activities and tasks in WP7. With the utilization of the functions and tools integrated in NNP the dissemination is intended to be, not as traditionally one way only, but active and two ways i.e. the beneficiaries and stakeholders being part of this new innovative environment for New Business Models in (C-) ITS.

Active communication and dissemination will be made possible through the use of social media, newsletter, CMS, YouTube Videos. These are some of the apps/ tools to be integrated in the NNP and used by Col members.

As it can be seen in the design of the Col, each of the three proposed tiers have specific scopes and members. After the initiation of the processes related to Tier 3, the Col will enhance visibility and outreach of key project outputs of NEWBITS to other stakeholders and regions. Since Tier3 is considered to be open, the promotion of the engagement of further stakeholders and end-users in NEWBITS activities will be also facilitated.

The liaison of EU and US stakeholders, providers of services, products and applications interested in both developing and adopting C-ITS solutions will be also fostered through the development of Tier 3 of the proposed Col. Expanding the network of contacts with actors, sharing partnerships and/or engagements is a crucial element.

3.1.2 Communities of Interest Configuration: Based on the four case studies

The NEWBITS partners have identified four case studies from the proposal stage that incorporate significant ITS solutions in the European ecosystem:

- CS1 (Spain): “VaoPoint” provides a solution for the growing demand on sustainable intercity mobility in European countries
- CS2 (Italy): C-ITS to manage the drivers’ behaviour crossing traffic lights intersections.
- CS3 (The Netherlands): New ICT method to increase efficiency in logistic chain of ports.
- CS4 (United Kingdom): “Keep Safe” - Predictive maintenance; Passengers’ safety and increased business performance in rail

3.1.3 Processes definition

It is important for the operation of the Col to follow specific processes that are going to guarantee their frictional operation and their sustainability. Processes will also support the evaluation of the Col.

A process is a set of tasks rationally associated to achieve a goal or perform a complex task. The goal of a process has to be achieved as quickly as possible. Therefore, the fewest possible steps should be included. Each step should be simple, well documented and clearly communicated. The process should be designed to be as friction-free as possible and quality be maintained at every step. A process is described by its goal(s); target participants; requirements; steps involved and a verification.

In the framework of the NEWBITS project the processes for the Col operation are codified as Tx.Py.Sz, more specifically:

- Tier Tx -> Tier levels (x=1,2,3)
- Process Py -> Process ID (y=1,2,3...n+1)
- Step Sz -> Step ID (z=1,2,3...n+1)

3.2 Col branding

The four distinct Col formed during the NEWBITS project will be built around the four case studies. In the NNP the four Col are realised as sub groups of an overarching Col. The attempt to brand and define them will be based on the exact features of each Col. Brief descriptions are provided below.

Note: These descriptions have been confirmed by the CS leaders, but they are expected to be expanded in future versions of the NNP. More detailed descriptions will be used to present the Col to the public and to motivate stakeholders to join.

3.2.1 Col 1: Sustainable Intercity Mobility: Intelligent carpooling services for city communities

- A Col built around intelligent carpooling and car-sharing services made possible by advanced C-ITS platforms that provide state of the art capabilities such as coordinating different route planners and providing real-time routing advice. The scope is to improve traffic flows, reduce emissions and increase urban road transport efficiency. End users also benefit from lower cost.
- A Col for a better quality of life in your daily transport with NEWBITS

3.2.2 Col 2: Efficient Traffic Management Services: An energy efficient service for city intersections

- A Col built around the installation and use of intelligent traffic management control systems that provide adaptive traffic control strategies, such as the installation of bi-directional communication system between traffic lights and vehicles, which instruct drivers on how to move efficiently in order to expend less time and energy in intersections. The scope is to improve the flow of traffic and reduce delays and carbon emissions.
- A Col to identify new and to expand business opportunities on collaborative intelligent transport systems.

3.2.3 Col 3: Synchro-modal solutions for goods transport on water: Using real-time data to decrease idle time and increase efficiency of hinterland transport

This Col is built around water transport efficiency-maximizing solutions using synchro-modality, which refers to the possibility of choosing the most optimal transport modality at transshipment points. This is achieved by collecting and transmitting real-time data on container transport, from ship tracking, container handling at port, inland ship and truck transport and handling of the containers at the inland terminal and eventually at the warehouse. The scope is to achieve better planning and shorter transport times by better insight into the logistics chain and the resulting decrease of idle time.

- A Col that improves the collaborative decision-making process across the various stakeholders.

3.2.4 Col 4: Railway customer satisfaction and safety: Predictive maintenance for cost reduction and safety in railway operation

A Col built around predictive maintenance for railway networks, identifying and reporting potential issues requiring repair before damages and delays appear. The scope is to improve service efficiency and increase passenger safety.

- A Col to foster a fully integrated business network modelling approach to railway industry.

3.3 Communities of Interest: Incentives

The issue of potential incentives that can be used to motivate stakeholders and actors into joining the Col Tiers 2 and 3, has been pointed out and discussed between the NEWBITS partners as willingness to participate in the Col is crucial to the success of the project. As a result, the issue of incentives to join the Col has been examined thoroughly. What follows is the result of a brief study on potential incentives that are used in forming Col.

The following four types of participants are identified as potential members of the Col. Each type can be motivated by different incentives which CSL have to identify and propose.

1. **The Collector:** It is in human nature to gather goods and status. Awards and achievements appeal to the desire for status. Other types of incentive programmes tap into this drive as well, motivating people through their desire to acquire more possessions.
2. **The Socializer:** Like it or not, we're wired to bond, and most of us experience the workplace first as a social setting. This is what makes recognition so powerful: celebrating stories about accomplishments with co-workers and managers makes people feel more appreciated.
3. **The Killer:** People are biologically motivated to defend what is theirs. The winner of last year's "Top in ..." title isn't going to let it go without a fight. And employees engaged by strong recognition programmes will work hard to protect their company against competitive threats.
4. **The Explorer:** People have an innate desire to contribute to something bigger in creative ways. Frequent acknowledgment of daily contributions connects us all to work in a more meaningful way, encouraging a higher level of commitment and more innovative thinking.

3.3.1 Incentives categories

Incentives can be categorised in the following: Practical; Financial; Social and Emotional. The following lists of incentives are not exclusive and can be modified. Each CSL, based upon the Col members and specificities will propose different incentives that will consider most appropriate and attract new members.

3.3.1.1 Practical incentives

Following is a list of practical incentives that can be used by CSL to promote each Col and attract potential members:

- Locked Content
- An eBook or Digital Document
- Free Trials
- Access to a Webinar or Other Event
- Consulting Time
- Educational Support

3.3.1.2 Financial incentives

Financial incentives are not foreseen by the grant agreement. Though, each CSL may identify potential financial incentives that can be offered by them without charging NEWBITS project. Financial incentives types include: Sponsored Benefits and Money off Discount Codes

3.3.1.3 Social incentives

Social incentives are considered quite important, especially since direct financial incentives are not foreseen. Social incentives can be in the form of fun or informative quizzes and a virtual “coffee break”. Social incentives with the support of the NNP requires mainly imagination by the CSL and commitment to virtual socialising rather than physical presence.

3.3.1.4 Emotional incentives

These incentives can be certificates of achievement; offers of “Idea bounties” and declaration of the monthly hero of a CoI based upon its involvement in it. CSL should use emotional incentives in intelligent ways to “provoke” the participation of members.

3.3.2 CoI-Specific Incentives

Different case-specific factors regarding potential incentives can be taken into consideration based on the specific nature and features of each CoI. These are based on feedback received from the four Case Study Leaders / CoI Leaders.

3.3.2.1 CoI 1 - UAB

Financial incentives are usually a main driver. However, in this case, financial incentives are not foreseen by the grant agreement. It is, possible, though, to open up the focus and deal not only with tangible but with intangible incentives, such as access to future benefits or access to funding sources, as we usually find in start-up accelerators environments.

The literature shows that incorporating economic incentives can even be counterproductive (Camerer & Hogarth, 1999), or that economic incentives have a tendency to increase quantity but not quality (Mason & Watts, 2009).

According to UAB as CS1 leader at the moment, it seems that the best incentives for CS1 / CoI1 are practical ones. Above all, the key incentive is being able to participate in the tool (intrinsic motivation) to generate synergies and networks that allow access to necessary resources to carry out a successful initiative (both financial resources and, chiefly, talent and knowledge). Therefore, the main incentive would be to be accepted in a group with the ability to access resources and talent. Therefore, the experience of participation must be the key to success and this experience of participation should allow the stakeholders to truly engage with access to content, training resources, webinars of controlled participation (not massive participation) etc.

For Tier 3, long-term work is required. Success will be achieved by a sufficient critical mass in terms of quantity but in any case, quality should not be neglected. An indiscriminate incorporation of participants will achieve the goal of quantity but can cause a problem of moderation because low quality participants that should not be accepted might discourage participation with contributions of minimum value. The need to preserve the quality of the participants, requires an

effort in the design of a protocol or acceptance mechanism that is easy and managed by the users themselves.

3.3.2.2 Col 2 - TTS

TTS as Col2 responsible partner proposed that would be a good idea to carefully think about how to fix a specific incentive budget (which might be CS-specific), if possible. This can depend on the target number of stakeholders and participants in general that will be targeted with incentives. Incentives should be offered straight after participants have joined and/or before they join to increase the chances of reaching a decent number of participants.

Specific possible incentives for CS2 / Col2 can include:

Practical incentives:

- E-book or digital document: This can be offered to a limited number of people joining, for example the first 100 stakeholders that will join receive a pre-selected ITS/transport-related publication/manual
- Free trials: This can be offered to anyone before they can make a decision to join the platform, an approach that can be connected to trialing the NNP platform.
- Access to webinars or events: This can work in a similar way to what was described for e-book incentive, i.e. transport-related events or training courses.

Financial incentives - the following two incentives are very effective for recruiting people.

- Vouchers
- Discount codes

Host networking opportunities where stakeholders can gather to discuss about a specific topic (via teleconference for example)

3.3.2.3 Col 3 - CED

CS3 and, to an extent, Col3, are related to very specific processes that require specific knowledge. As part of Col3 processes, members must be informed about container transport processes (terminal processes, containers release processes etc.), the container transport value chain and its different characteristics (terminal processes, containers release processes etc.), and in understanding container transport, as it is essential having background knowledge to understand the added value and needs of the service developed in CS3. Even logistical operators do not always have complete knowledge of the activities of other operators in the transport chain.

The relevant parties that will provide information will be identified. The information will be prepared in a way that is easy to understand without losing too much detail, relevant channels for distributing the information will be identified, and movies, webinars and other means to provide information will be shared via the NNP.

Col members can be engaged to share their desire about further service development, proposing possibilities to extend the value proposition of the service. This can allow the formation of more specialized incentives.

3.3.2.4 Col 4 - CUE

In terms of practical incentives, for CS4 / Col4, engagement with the public could prove valuable. This would provide an additional channel for the railway industry to communicate with and learn from passengers on very specific topics such as reliability of the services or security and safety. Specific financial incentives are hard to identify for CS4 / Col4 due to the way in which the funding of the original case study was determined.

In terms of social incentives, a rail passenger forum will certainly help develop a community that informs areas of future research and developments. This is the kind of discussion that may take place at a Station Café.

Col4, as an extension of CS4, should draw potential members from the following stakeholder categories: Train Manufacturers, Academic Institutions, Educators, Railway Infrastructure Owners, Government institutions, Rail Regulators, Safety regulators, the Public, IT Service companies, and Train Operators.

A study can be conducted about the value that each of them expects from the case study / Col and from other stakeholders within the case study / Col.

Then, a study can be conducted on how the Col can help achieve these. For example, how it can assist government institutions have the public perspective on railway safety, or help educators have a better understanding of railway and C-ITS knowledge. This can be used to offer better, customized incentives for Col4.

3.4 Tier 1: Communities of Interest internally support NEWBITS WPs

Tier 1 of the Col is essentially internal, consisting of the consortium and its primary aim is to support the NEWBITS project WP activities that are relevant to the Col. It has been initially set in motion since M08 of the project. Its goals and processes are: To support the benchmarking of ITS innovations: EU vs US (WP3); To support mapping exercise of value flows (WP4); To support the development of (C-) ITS business case guidelines (WP5) and the evaluation of risks and benefits of the new business models (WP5). Tier 1 processes flow is presented in Figure 47.

Tier 1: All processes

- T1.P1 Invitation of members
- T1.P2 Benchmarking ITS innovations: EU vs US
- T1.P3 Mapping exercise of value flows
- T1.P4 Development of (C-) ITS business case guidelines
- T1.P5 Evaluation of risks and benefits of the new business models

Figure 47 Tier 1: Processes flow

3.5 Tier 2: Advanced Communities of Interest of C-ITS experts

Tier 2 of the Col will operate as an advanced group of C-ITS experts, which, in effect, can form a middle ground or testbed for Tier 3, which will be completely open to the public. Tier 2 is still very important, however, as it consists of major stakeholders that are central to the four case studies and therefore, crucial for the operation of the Col that will be based on them. Target participants can be from: the consortium; the SAB and CS stakeholders. Tier 2 goals are the following:

- G2.1 Networking
- G2.2 Knowledge transfer
- G2.3 Development of common initiatives (Projects EC Funded and national, private)
- G2.4 Formation of interest groups

Tier 2: All processes presented on Figure 48

- T2 P1 Identification of members
- T2.P2 Invitation of new members
- T2.P3 Engagement of members to new EC funded projects
- T2.P4 Engagement of members to new national funded projects
- T2.P5 Engagement of members to new academic initiatives
- T2.P6 Engagement of members to new private research projects
- T2.P7 Engagement of members to interest groups
- T2.P8 Conflict management between members

Figure 48 Tier 2: Processes flow

3.5.1 T2.P1 Identification of members

Identification of CS stakeholders will be performed by: consortium partners; CS leaders; CS Stakeholders and SAB.

Included steps in the process:

- T2.P1.S1 stakeholder identification / mapping (WP2 D2.3)
- T2.P1.S2 stakeholder analysis (WP3 D3.1)
- T2.P1.S3 stakeholders mapping (WP6 D6.1)

3.5.2 T2.P2 Invitation of new members

A formal invitation addressed to SAB members and CS Stakeholders will be sent by: CS Leaders; Consortium Partners; SAB members and CS Stakeholders.

Included steps in the process:

- T2.P2.S1 Conduction of potential list of members
- T2.P2.S2 Formulation of invitation letter

- T2.P2.S3 Distribution of invitation
- T2.P2.S4 Contact invitation participants
- T2.P2.S5 Monitoring of the process

3.5.3 T2.P3 Engagement of members to new EC-funded projects

The process aims to increase the number of EC-funded project proposals that each member participates. Responsible for the process are: CS Leaders; Consortium Partners; SAB and CS Stakeholders.

The implementation of the process requires the identification of calls for proposals; selection of the most relative calls and the dissemination to the members of the most relative ones.

Included steps in the process:

- T2.P3.S1 Identification of potential EC-funded project calls
- T2.P3.S2 Posting of new EC-funded project calls to members
- T2.P3.S3 Express of interest
- T2.P3.S4 Pursuit of new EC-funded projects by consortia of members
- T2.P3.S5 Monitoring of the process

3.5.3.1 T2.P3.S1 Identification of potential EC-funded project calls

Figure 49 presents how to identify potential EC-funded project calls. First identification of information sources is performed and then continuous monitoring of these sources. INTELS as WP6 leader with the collaboration of CSL will monitor different sources and inform CoI members.

Figure 49 T2.P3.S1 Identification of potential EC funded project calls

3.5.3.2 T2.P3.S2 Posting of new EC-funded project calls to members

Figure 50 presents the flow of tasks that have to be performed in order to inform Col members about EC-funded project calls. Each member has to login in the NNP and then posts the identified EC funded project calls. Col members are informed via e-mail, for the identified call that appears in NNP.

Figure 50 T2.P3.S2 Posting of new EC-funded project calls to members

3.5.3.3 T2.P3.S3 Express of interest

A potential project leader can send invitation to specific members (that can be hidden) or create an open call of interest, following potential project partners expression of availability. Members of Col invite potential partners, while NNP facilitates the communication and holds only the transaction not the content. Figure 51 presents the flow of tasks in this step.

Figure 51 T2.P3.S3 Express of interest

3.5.3.4 T2.P3.S4 Pursuit of new EC funded projects by consortia of members

The specific step is supporting the idea generation process and proposed project consortium building. Any Col member can initiate the step while NNP facilitates the step without storing any content. NNP via the private discussion forum functionality supports this task.

Figure 52 T2.P3.S4 Pursuit of new EC-funded projects by consortia of members

3.5.3.5 T2.P3.S5 Monitoring of the process

Each process is proposed to include a monitoring step for which is proposed to define specific performance indicators. Monitoring will be implemented in total during the pilot operation of the NNP and it is proposed to be further elaborated after the pilot NNP operation during the project life cycle.

Figure 53 T2.P3.S5 Monitoring of the process

How to	Who does what
1. Define performance indicators per step	INTELS with the validation of CSL(s)
2. Define measurement techniques for each indicator	INTELS with the validation of CSL(s)
3. Define periodicity of measurement	INTELS with the validation of CSL(s)
4. Apply monitoring	INTELS with the support of CSL(s)
NNP should visualise monitoring results to enhance users' engagement	

3.5.4 T2.P4 Engagement of members to new national funded projects

This process aims to increase the number of national funded project proposals that each member participates in. This process will be implemented by: CS Leaders; Consortium Partners; SAB and the CS Stakeholders.

The steps included in this process are similar of those described in T2.P3. Firstly, the identification of calls for proposals should be implemented and then members should select the most relative calls. Finally, the dissemination of the most relative calls to the Col members follows. The foreseen steps included in T2.P4 are the following:

- T2.P4.S1 Identification of potential national project calls
- T2.P4.S2 Posting of new national project calls to members
- T2.P4.S3 Pursuit of new national projects by consortia of members
- T2.P4.S4 Monitoring of the process

3.5.5 T2.P5 Engagement of members to new academic initiatives

It aims to increase the number of academic initiatives that each member participates in. The following are considered as academic initiatives: Research papers, Research projects, PhDs, common curricula.

In this process, CS Leaders, SAB and academic members are involved.

The process is initiated with the identification of academic initiatives opportunities. Then members should proceed to the selection of the most relative opportunities and disseminate them to other Col members. The foreseen steps included in T2.P5 are the following:

- T2.P5.S1 Identification of new academic initiatives
- T2.P5.S2 Posting of new academic initiatives to the related subgroup of members (Academia)

- T2.P5.S3 Pursuit of new academic initiatives by consortia of members (the related subgroup)
- T2.P5.S4 Monitoring of the process

3.5.6 T2.P6 Engagement of members to new private research projects

It aims to increase the number of private funded research projects that each member participates in. The process will be implemented by: CS Leaders; Consortium Partners; SAB and the CS Stakeholders.

The process focuses on enterprises, Col members, to publish research projects opportunities. The foreseen steps included in T2.P6 are the following:

- T2.P6.S1 Identification of new private research projects
- T2.P6.S2 Posting of new private research projects to all Col members
- T2.P6.S3 Pursuit of new private research by consortia of members.
- T2.P6.S4 Monitoring of the process

3.5.7 T2.P7 Engagement of members to interest groups

Aims to provide information and advice to associations, organizations and experts so that policy makers do not make decisions in isolation. The process will be implemented by: CS Leaders; Consortium Partners; SAB and CS Stakeholders.

During the process the identification of key themes related to C-ITS and Col members should take place. Afterwards members can identify opportunities to promote their interest. The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T2.P7.S1 Strategies design
 - Pro-active; Reactive; Defensive
- T2.P7.S2 Strategies implementation
- T2.P7.S3 Involvement to Tactics
 - Drawing others into C-ITS landscape – ecosystem
 - Defending public interests
 - Pressure
- T2.P7.S4 Monitoring of the process

3.5.8 T2.P8 Conflict management between members

This process aims to minimise as possible the interaction of interdependent people who perceive opposition of goals, aims, and values, and who see the other party as potentially interfering with the realization of these goals. All members of the Col would be potential interested in the process. Key steps in T2.P8 Conflict management between members are:

- T2.P8.S1 Conflict identification: Continuous monitoring
- T2.P8.S2 Conflict analysis
- T2.P8.S3 Addressing options identification
- T2.P8.S4 Application of conflict resolution techniques
 - Resolve through collaboration
 - Resolve through avoidance
 - Resolve through compromise (Bargaining and Negotiation)
- T2.P8.S5 Review of the conflict impact

3.6 Tier 3: Communities of Interest to promote C-ITS Solutions

Tier 3 of the Col represents the external, “complete” and open form of the Col, oriented and marketed to the public to promote C-ITS in society, presenting the successful realization of ITS / C-ITS solutions. It will include all relevant parties, from consortium members, to ITS / C-ITS stakeholders of all sizes, to the general public. Its goals and processes are outlined here. CS leaders are expected to contribute relevant content for all Col actions. Members of Tier 3 will be NEWBITS consortium members; voluntarily CS stakeholders and as described previously will be open to whom it may concern (Public).

Foreseen goals of Tier 3 include the following:

- G3.1 Crowd sourcing (Raise awareness on the state of the art on the fields)
- G3.2 Crowd funding (“StarterFund” based on KickStarter)
- G3.3 Match making suppliers and customers
- G3.4 Networking
- G3.5 Making ITS C-ITS visible to the society
- G3.6 Learning NEWBITS model

Key processes that will take place in Tier 3 are the following as presented in Figure 54.

- T3.P1 C-ITS awareness raising
- T3.P2 Enrolment of new members to Tier 3
- T3.P3 Verification / acceptance of new members
- T3.P4 Engagement of members to crowd sourcing tasks
- T3.P5 Engagement of members to crowd funding tasks
- T3.P6 Implementation of an e-learning module on NEWBITS
- T3.P7 Conflict management between members
- T3.P8 Monitoring Tier 3 progress

Figure 54 Tier 3 Processes flow

3.6.1 T3.P1 C-ITS awareness raising

The scope of the P1 in Tier3 is to raise the awareness around ITS and C-ITS. Topics that related information should be published are the following: Technologies; Initiatives / Projects; Products / services and Applications. Information will be shared in the Col by: CS Leaders; CS Stakeholders; Academic members; Enterprises and Local authorities. The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T3.P1.S1 Setting objectives
- T3.P1.S2 Identification of target groups
- T3.P1.S3 Identification of information sources
- T3.P2.S4 Publishing information
- T3.P1.S5 Are you interested in participating?
- T3.P1.S6 Monitoring of the process

3.6.2 T3.P2 Enrolment of new members to Tier 3

This process is about enrolling members for processes T3.P4; T3.P5; T3.P6. Col members can be from any of the quadruple helix as: Academia; Business; Local authorities and Citizens. Special attention should be given in the NNP on the Personal Data protection statement to fulfil the GDPR requirements. During the implementation of the NNP users' profile and the enrolment form should be carefully designed to respect GDPR and also the privacy of the members.

The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T3.P2.S1 Enrolment form: Personal data
- T3.P2.S2 Profiling of users
- T3.P2.S3 Monitoring the process

3.6.3 T3.P3 Verification / acceptance of new members

The NNP is foreseen as a valid self-sustained ecosystem to support market launch and adoption of ©-ITS products and services. The verification / acceptance of new members is proposed to be performed by: CS Leaders and CS Stakeholders. INTELS as WP6 leader will support and monitor in a broad perspective the enrolment of new members.

The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T3.P3.S1 CS leaders verify through social networks the new members
- T3.P3.S2 Acceptance / Rejection of application
- T3.P3.S3 Monitoring the process

3.6.4 T3.P4 Engagement of members to crowd sourcing tasks

The process is considered as one of the innovative services that the Col can provide to the members. The concept is that certain members may want to outsource a specific set of functions to an undefined set of people, instead of assigning it to designated employees. This process can be triggered by: CS Leaders; CS Stakeholders; Academia; Enterprises and Local authorities.

The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T3.P4.S1 Micro-task Markets
- T3.P4.S2 Open Innovation Contests
- T3.P4.S3 Initialisation
 - Task designing
 - Task breakdown
 - Incentive design
- T3.P4.S4 Implementation
- Finding crowd
- Task assigning
- T3.P4.S5 Finalization
 - Quality control
 - Aggregation
- T3.P4.S6 Monitoring the process

3.6.5 T3.P5 Engagement of members to crowd funding tasks

This process is considered quite important for the sustainability of the Col and NNP. Via this process the implementation of crowdfunding fundraising campaigns to support the market launch of C-ITS solutions will be supported. Crowdfunding campaigns will be triggered by: CS Leaders; CS Stakeholders; Academia; Enterprises and Local authorities.

Col is proposed to create and present a pool of prototypes / ideas to potential funders. The NNP will support the proposed process and should have the ability to present legal support documentation. The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T3.P5.S1 Submission of prototypes / ideas (Have to decided)

- T3.P5.S2 Members use story-telling to promote prototype / ideas YouTube (NNP connection with YouTube?)
- T3.P5.S3 Definition of rewards for initial backers
- T3.P5.S4 Determination of a realistic amount and time to complete the proposed product / service
- T3.P5.S5 Sharing through social media
- T3.P5.S6 Engagement with backers during the process
- T3.P5.S7 Monitoring of the process

3.6.6 T3.P6 Implementation of an e-learning module on NEWBITS

The scope of the process is to educate Col members through self-paced; cost effective; faster; consistent and easily managed course on the proposed NEWBITS business model. Members interested in this process will be: Academia; Enterprises and local authorities.

To be able to execute this process the e-learning module on NEWBITS new business model is required.

The process is proposed to include the following steps:

- T3.P6.S1 Personalized learning via NNP
- T3.P6.S2 Monitoring individual progress
- T3.P6.S3 Members engagement and motivation
- T3.P6.S4 Collection of additional resources
- T3.P6.S5 Allocation of supporting experts
- T3.P6.S6 Monitoring the process

3.7 Members involvement

In previous sections have been in detailed presented key processes that will take place during the Col operation. This section refers to the support of the Col smooth operation through the participation of NEWBITS consortium members to each process. The performed in-depth analysis of the Col functions and the stakeholders, drove us to this rather complicated Col operational manual. The aforementioned described procedures are considered as the sole way to have a sustainable Col that will attract members not only during the NEWBITS project life cycle but afterwards as well.

	INTELS	CSL	SAB	Cols members
T1.P1 Invitation of members	✓	✓	✓	
T1.P2 Benchmarking ITS innovations: EU vs US		✓	✓	
T1.P3 Mapping exercise of value flows		✓	✓	
T1.P4 Development of (C-) ITS business case guidelines		✓	✓	
T1.P5 Evaluation of risks and benefits of the new business models		✓	✓	

Figure 55 Tier 1: Who implements the processes

	INTELS	CSL	SAB	Cols members
T2.P1 Identification of members	✓	✓	✓	✓
T2.P2 Invitation of new members		✓	✓	✓
T2.P3 Engagement to new EC funded projects		✓	✓	✓
T2.P4 Engagement to new national funded projects		✓	✓	✓
T2.P5 Engagement to new academic initiatives		✓	✓	✓
T2.P6 Engagement to new private research projects		✓	✓	✓
T2.P7 Engagement to interest groups		✓	✓	
T2.P8 Conflict management between members	✓			

Figure 56 Tier 2: Who implements the processes

	INTELS	CSL	SAB	Cols members
T3.P1 C-ITS awareness raising	✓	✓	✓	✓
T3.P2 Enrolment of new members to Tier 3		✓		✓
T3.P3 Verification / acceptance of new members		✓		
T3.P4 Engagement of members to crowd sourcing tasks		✓		✓
T3.P5 Engagement of members to crowd funding tasks		✓	✓	✓
T3.P6 Implementation of an e-learning module on NEWBITS		✓	✓	✓
T3.P7 Conflict management between members	✓			
T3.P8 Monitoring Tier 3 progress	✓			

Figure 57 Tier 3: Who implements the processes

3.8 Task allocation to partners for creation and operation of the Cols

3.8.1 Partner A: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Cols

Partner A	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/ services	T1: No further input required T2: Executive feedback and support on Goals T3: Executive feedback and support on Goals
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	
Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.2 Partner B: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Cols

Partner B	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/ services	T1: No further input required T2: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CS1 T3: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CS1
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner B is not WPL hence no input required T2: Further elaboration of the processes in the scope of CSx T3: Further elaboration of the process in the scope of CSx
Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.3 Partner C: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Cols

Partner C	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/ services	T1: No further input required T2: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CSy T3: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CSy
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner C is WPy Leader hence no input required T2: Further elaboration of the processes in the scope of CSy T3: Further elaboration of the process in the scope of CSy

Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.4 Partner D: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Communities of Interest

Partner D	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/services	T1: No further input required T2: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CSy T3: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CSy
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner D is not WPL hence no input required T2: Further elaboration of the processes in the scope of CSy T3: Further elaboration of the process in the scope of CSz
Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.5 Partner E: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Cols

Partner E	Expected input
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Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/services	T1; T2; T3: No further input required
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner E is WPz Leader input required on the processes. To support the benchmarking of ITS innovations: EU vs US
Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.6 Partner F: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Communities of Interest

Partner F	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/services	T1: No further input required T2: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CSz T3: Further elaboration of Goals, Incentives derived mainly from CSz
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner F is WPx Leader input required on the processes. To support the development of (C-) ITS business case guidelines and the evaluation of risks and benefits of the new business models. T2: Further elaboration of the processes in the scope of CSy T3: Further elaboration of the process in the scope of CSy
Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.7 Partner G: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Communities of Interest

Partner G	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/services	T1; T2; T3: No further input required
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner G is WPx Leader no processes are foreseen T2: Support on the visibility of the tier T3: Support on the visibility of the tier
Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

3.8.8 Partner H: Sub task 6.1.2 Creation and Operation of the Communities of Interest

Partner H	Expected input
Case study analysis to identify Cols key features/services	T1; T2; T3: No further input required
Col Guidelines: to guarantee that all Cols will follow the same approach.	T1: Partner H is not WPL T2: Support on the visibility of the tier T3: Support on the visibility of the tier

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Review of Cols guidelines by the consortium	Executive review and feedback on the guidelines: all tiers and processes
Cols initiation stage by Case study leaders	

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5 Appendix I: Data gathering instructions for the preliminary mapping

The following instructions correspond to the columns of a spreadsheet provided to all partners for data gathering.

5.1 Instructions for the stakeholder verification process (3/5/2017)

Column J – Verified: Can it be verified (via personal contact or via the official website) that the stakeholder is still in its/his/her stated position or still active in the field of ITS? Write yes or no.

Column K – Organization / Entity url: The website url of the organization or an individual's private website, if available.

Column L – LinkedIn profile url: The url for the LinkedIn profile of the individual note in column A, if available.

Column M – Related stakeholders IDs: If a person has moved to a new organization or if the organization has replaced the person named in column A with another one then make a new entry to the list and mention the link with this new entry in this box (e.g. "Mr. Gonzalez is working in a different organization, new entry added to row 456").

5.2 Instructions for the data gathering (12/5/2017)

Column N – Location: The location and/or address of the stakeholder. This is the organization's address or the address of a person's office.

Column O – Type (aligned with D.2.1): Please fill in one of the options below. If other than specify.

- a. Industry
- b. Academia
- c. Policy makers
- d. Other (please specify)

Column P – Focused ITS area Market Segments (aligned with D.2.1): Please fill in one or more of the options below, as applicable.

- a. Advanced Traveler Information Systems (ATIS)
- b. Advanced Traffic Management System (ATMS)
- c. Advanced Transportation Pricing System (ATPS)
- d. Advanced Public Transportation System (APTS)
- e. Cooperative Vehicle System (CVS)
- f. All of the above

Column Q – Target Market: Please fill in one or more of the options below. If other than specify.

- a. Private
- b. Public
- c. B2B
- d. Other (please specify)

Column R – Brief Profile: Please provide a brief profile of the stakeholder in the box. This can be an organization’s profile and history, or a very brief CV of an individual.

Column S – Main ITS Activities: Please describe the main products, services and/or activities of the stakeholder in the box. Organizations will have products or services while individuals will have main activities.

Column T – Connected Organizations:

Column U – Types of Outputs and Deliverables:

Column V – Stakeholder Interest:

Column W – Stakeholder Power:

Column X – Stakeholder Attitude:

6 Appendix II: Stakeholders and identified types

Type	Number of identified entities
Acquaintances	2
Friends	27
Irritants	13
Saboteurs	9
Saviours	78
Sleeping giants	4
Time Bombs	11
Trip Wires	22
	166

7 Appendix III: List of unique organisations

Organisation	Appearances
5T	1
ACI	1
ALG	1
ATM - Metropolitan Transport Authority (Barcelona area)	1

D6.1 Col Configuration Synthesis Report (Intermediate deliverable)

Organisation	Appearances
ATV	1
Aalborg University	1
Alexander Innovation Zone SA	1
Antea Group	2
Aragon Institute of Technology	1
Aslogic	1
Association of Information Technology Companies of Northern Greece (SEPVE)	1
AustriaTech	3
Autostrade per l'Italia	1
Barcelona City Council	1
Belgrade Public Transportation	1
Birmingham City Council	2
CE Delft	4
CEREMA - Ministry of Transport	1
CORTE Secretariat	1
CRF	1
CTAG - Galician Automotive Technology Centre	2
Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - CERTH	3
Comune di Roma	1
Conigital Group	1
Connekt/ITS Netherlands	1
Coventry University	3
Coventry University Enterprises Ltd	1
De Lijn	1
Department of Maritime Studies, University of Piraeus	1
Dpt of Mechanical Engineering, Univ. of Western Macedonia	1
Dynniq	1
EPIKINONIA Ltd	1

D6.1 Col Configuration Synthesis Report (Intermediate deliverable)

Organisation	Appearances
ERF (European Road Federation)	2
ERTICO	2
EURECAT	1
EcoTelematics - SIA	1
Egnatia Odos S.A.	1
Emphasis Telematics SA	1
Europea Commission, Joint Research Centre	1
European Metropolitan Transport Authorities	1
European Passengers Federation	1
Fundación Axencia Intermunicipal da Enerxía de Vigo	1
Gemeente Zwolle	1
Goudappel Coffeng	1
Highway Engineering Laboratory, Dpt of Transportation and Project Management, School of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering AUTH	1
Hogia UK (Hogia Transport Systems Ltd)	1
INFOTRIP -Intelligent Transportation Systems	1
INTELSPACE innovation Technologies SA	1
IQ Taxi Inc	1
IRF (international Road Federation)	1
IRU	1
ISINNOVA	1
ITS America	1
ITS Argentina	1
ITS Australia	1
ITS Belgium	1
ITS China	1
ITS Czech & Slovak	1
ITS Denmark	1
ITS Finland	1

D6.1 CoI Configuration Synthesis Report (Intermediate deliverable)

Organisation	Appearances
ITS France	1
ITS Germany	1
ITS Hong Kong	1
ITS Ireland	1
ITS Israel	1
ITS Malta	1
ITS Norway	1
ITS Portugal	1
ITS Romania	1
ITS Shenzhen	1
ITS Singapore / LTA Singapore	1
ITS Spain	1
ITS Sweden	1
ITS Taiwan	1
ITS UK	1
Illumineight	1
Instantic	1
Jacobs	1
KTH Royal Institute of Technology	1
LNEC - Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (National Laboratory for Civil Engineering)	1
Latvian Logistics Association	1
Lindholmen Science Park	1
MTORRES DISEÑOS INDUSTRIALES SAU	1
MaaS Global	1
Magneti Marelli	1
Mail&Boxes (Logistics Operator)	1
Mattersoft FI	1
MeMex srl	1

D6.1 CoI Configuration Synthesis Report (Intermediate deliverable)

Organisation	Appearances
Ministry of Transport	1
Moving forward consulting	1
Municipality of Thessaloniki	1
Nommon Solutions and Technologies	1
Open Knowledge Greece	1
Optibus	1
Ortelio Ltd	1
POLIS	1
Pluservice	1
Politecnico di Milano	1
Polito	1
Prisma Electronics	1
Provincie Gelderland	1
RMIT	1
Region of Western Macedonia	1
Rey Juan Carlos University Face Recognition and Artificial Vision Research Laboratory (FRAV)	1
Ricardo	1
Rijkswaterstaat	1
SERNAUTO	1
SINTEF	1
SWD Factory SIA	1
School of Spatial Planning and Development, Faculty of Engineering, AUTH	1
Steinbeis 2i GmbH	1
Strane Innovation	1
Swarco	1
TIS	1
TMB - Transports Metropolitans de Barcelona	1
TNO	1

D6.1 Col Configuration Synthesis Report (Intermediate deliverable)

Organisation	Appearances
TREDIT S.A	1
TRENOLab	1
TU Eindhoven	1
Technical University of Chemnitz, Faculty of Economics and Business Administration	1
Technical University of Munich	1
Tom Tom/ TUE	1
Tool Alfa	1
Tramvia Metropolitana, SA	1
Transport Engineering Laboratory, Dpt of Transportation and Project Management, School of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, AUTH	1
Transport and Telecommunication Institute	2
Transport for London	2
Treelogic	1
TÜV Rheinland Consulting GmbH	1
UPC	1
URENIO Research, School of Architecture,AUTH	1
US DOT	1
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid	1
Universidad de Alcalá	1
Universidad de Deusto, DeustoTech-Mobility	1
Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria	1
Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona	1
University Naples	1
University Southampton	1
University of Aberdeen	1
University of Belgrade	1
University of Borås: Innovation Lab at the school of Business and informatics	1
University of Leeds	1

Organisation	Appearances
University of Zaragoza /GITEL	1
VTI	1
Verona Municipality	1
Welgood Solutions	1
Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy >Resigned in August 2016	1
Zurich University of Applied Sciences	1
websms	1
Total	166

8 Appendix IV: Members of identified clusters

8.1 Vertex Group 1

Connekt/ITS Netherlands; ITS Finland; Rijkswaterstaat; 24RENT; 2GETTHERE; 3DS; AALTO; ABAX; ADA; ADVIN; AEF; AGORA_CENTER; AKL; AMSTERDAM; ANDES; ANTEAGROUP; ANTWERPMANAGEMENTSCHOOL; ANWB; APPM; Arctic_Power; ARRIVA; ARS; ASTRIN; ATOSBORNE; AUTOMOTIVENL; AVY; BCIGLOBAL; BEAMRZ; BERENSCHOT; Bergmann_Attorneys; BIMBIMBIKES; BNVMOBILITY; BOSTEC; BOVAG; BRABANT; CALENDAR42; CAPGEMINI; CASHBYCYCLING; CBR; Centre for Economic Development, Transport and the Environment (ELY Centre); CENTRIA; CGI; CGI Finland Oy; CINIA; CIRCULARISE; City of Tampere; CITY_CAR_CLUB; CLIMATENEUTRALGROUP; CONNECTIONSYSTEMS; CONNEKT; CONNEXXION; CROW; DEGROENEHUB; DELOITTE; DISTRICON; DRIVECO; DRIVENBYHELMOND; DTVCONSULTANTS; DUTCH; Dutch Government (I&M); DXC.TECHNOLOGY; DYNNIQ; EASYPARK; EATECH; ECORYS; ECT; EEE_Innovations; EkoRent; EkoRent Oy; ELY_Centre; EMBELIN; ENIGMACONSULTING; EVOFENEDEX; FICONIC; Finnish Bus and Coach Association; Finnish Central Organisation for Motor Trades and Repairs; Finnish Driving Schools Association; Finnish Ministry of Transport and Communications; Finnish Transport Agency; Finnish Transport Safety Agency Trafic; Finnish_Driving_Schools_Association; Finnish_Motor_Insurers'_Centre; Finnish_Transport_Safety_Agency; FINNPARK; FLEVOLAND; FLORIADE; FMI; FORECA; GELDERLAND; GOSWIFT; GOUDAPPEL; GS1; GVB; HAMK; HAN; HARDTGLOBALMOBILITY; HEIJMANS; HELLOGO; HELPTEN; HELSINKI; Helsinki Region Transport HRT (HSL); HIIT; HSL; IBM; INDAGON; INFOTRIPLA; INMOVES; INNOFACTORY; INTERSARTO; INTERTRAFFIC; INTRAFFIC; iQ Payments Oy; JAMK; KPN; LELYSTADAIRPORTBUSINESSPARK; LEVI9; Liikenneturva; LIMBURG; LINJA-AUTOLIITTO; Linkker; LOGISTIHKAYRITYSTEN_LIITTO_RY; LVRA; LVW; MaaS Finland Oy; MaaS_Global; MAPTM; Matkahuolto; Mattersoft; MAZARS; MDI; Mediamobile; MICPOINT; MINDMOBILITY; MOBILITYBEL; MOBILITYSENSING; Mobisoft; MRDH; MYPO; National Land Survey of Finland NLS; NDW; NEDAPIDENTIFICATION; NESTRA; NEVIA; NEXT-MOBILITY; NHTV; NLS; NMI;

NOORD-HOLLAND; NOPTTEL; OC; OCDM; ORTANA; OULU_UNIVERSITY; P2; PAR; PARKFLYRENT; PAYIQ; Perille_Mobility_Services; PiggyBaggy; PIIRLA; PITPOINT; PNOCONSULTANTS; PORTOFROTTERDAM; PROCAP; PTVGROUP; RAILFORUM; RAINBOWMANAGEMENT; RAIVERENIGING; RDW; RETOURPLAZA; RICARDO; RIETVELD; RIJKSOVERHEID; RMC-NEDERLAND; ROADSCANNERS; ROBOTTUNER; ROUTE42; ROYALHASKONINGDHV; SATEL; SATELBV; SCHIPHOL; SCOOSY; SEMEL; Semel Oy; SENSYSGATSO; Shareit_Blox_Car

8.2 Vertex Group 2

ITS America; ITS Malta; A+I+C; AAA; Activu Corporation; Ada County Highway District; ADOT; AECOM; America Council on Renewable Energy; American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials; American Highway Users Alliance; American Public Transportation Association; American Traffic Safety Services Association; Arkansas Highway and Transportation Department; ASTI Transportation Systems Inc.; AUTOTALKS LTD; Blynco; Brandmotion, LLC; C. Douglas Couto – Individual; California Path - UC Berkeley; Caltrans; Canadien Wireless Telecom Association; Car Buddy Corporation; Carol Schweiger - Individual; CATT Laboratory; Central Florida Regional Transportation Authority – LYNX; CH2M; Citizens Conservation Corps; City of Chicago; City of Novi; City of Orlando; City of Philadelphia; City of San Antonio; Club touring Malta; Colorado DOT; Commercial Vehicle Safety Alliance; Compass Transportation & Technology Inc.; Comtrol Corporation; Connect Baltica; Consensus Systems Technologies Corp.; Contra Costa Transportation Authority; Control Technologies; Crown Castle; Daktronics; Department of Transportation; Derq; DGD Enterprises, Inc. - Individual; Digital Traffic Systems, Inc.; Douglas County DOT; Driversiti; EasyMile; Eberle Design Inc.; Econolite Group, Inc.; ERoad; EX2 Technology, LLC; FDOT; Federal Highway Administration; Federal Motor Carrier Safety Administration; Federal Railroad Administration; Federal Transit Administration; FM; Fortis Consulting; Georgia DOT; GEWI; Global Traffic Technologies, LLC; Gresham Smith and Partners; GRIDSMART; Gurdas S. Sandhu – Student; Hawaii DOT; HDR, Inc.; HELP Inc. – Provider of PrePass; HNTB; Illinois DOT; Illinois State Toll Highway Authority; Image Sensing Systems, Inc.; Institute of Transportation Engineers; Intercomp; Intermodal Association of North America; International Bridge, Tunnel & Turnpike Association; International Municipal Signal Association; International Road Federation; Iowa DOT; iteris; ITS Canada; ITS Columbia; ITS Ireland; ITS United Kingdom; Kimley-Horn and Associates, Inc.; KLD Engineering, P.C.; Laser Technology Inc.; Los Angeles County Department of Public Works; Los Angeles County MTA; Louisiana DOT and Development; M city University of Michigan; M.H. Corbin; Macomb County Department of Roads; Maricopa County DOT; Maryland DOT; Massachusetts Institute of Technology; McCain, Inc.; Metro Transit (Minneapolis/St. Paul); Metropolitan Transit Authority of Harris County; Metropolitan Transportation Commission; Michigan Department of Transportation; Mid-America Regional Council; Mid-Region Council of Governments; Miovision; Missouri DOT; Motogo; Moxa Americas, Inc.; MultiLife; Municipality of Anchorage; National Center for Atmospheric Research; National Highway Institute; National Highway Traffic Safety Administration; National Operations Center of Excellence; National Renewable Energy Laboratory; Nevada DOT; New York City DOT; New York State DOT; Noblis; Northrop Grumman;

NXP Semiconductor; Ontario Ministry of Transportation; Oregon DOT; Panasonic; Parsons Corporation; Peek Traffic Corporation; Peloton Technology; Pennsylvania DOT; Peracchio & Company, LLC; Phoenix Contact, Inc.; Pierce Transit; Pinellas County; Port Authority of New York & New Jersey; QUALCOMM; Road Commission for Oakland County; RoadBotics; Ross & Baruzzini, Inc.; RTC; Sakura Associates LLC; San Francisco Municipal Transportation Agency (SFMTA); Security Design Professionals, LLC; Sensys Networks, Inc.; SERCO; SGS Testcom, Inc.; Shelley Row – Individual

8.3 Vertex Group 3

5T; ACI; ALG; ATM - Metropolitan Transport Authority (Barcelona area); ATV; Aslogic; AustriaTech; Barcelona City Council ; CE Delft; CEREMA - Ministry of Transport; CRF; Centre for Research and Technology Hellas - CERTH; Coventry University Enterprises Ltd; ERTICO; EURECAT; Europea Commission, Joint Research Centre; European Passengers Federation; INFOTRIP -Intelligent Transportation Systems; Illumineight; KTH Royal Institute of Technology; LNEC - Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil (National Laboratory for Civil Engineering); Lindholmen Science Park; MTORRES DISEÑOS INDUSTRIALES SAU; MaaS Global; Magneti Marelli; Mail&Boxes (Logistics Operator); Mattersoft FI ; MeMex srl; Ministry of Transport; Moving forward consulting; Ortelio Ltd; Pluservice; Polito; RMIT; SERNAUTO; Steinbeis 2i GmbH; Swarco; TMB - Transports Metropolitans de Barcelona; Tramvia Metropolitana, SA; Transport for London; Treelogic; UPC; Universidad Carlos III de Madrid; Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona; University Naples; University of Belgrade; University of Leeds; Verona Municipality; Wuppertal Institute for Climate, Environment and Energy; ACEA European Automobile Manufacturers Association; Aerospace Valley (AV); ALG; Anaptyxiaki Grevenon-Anaptyxiaki Anonymi Etaireia Ota; APPLUS IDIADA; ASCOM; Aslogic; Asstra (Italian public transport association); ATM; Audi; Austratech; Austrian Institute of Technology; Austrian Ministry of Transport, Innovation and Technology (bmvit); AustriaTech; Autovie Venete; AVENIR MOBILITÉ | ZUKUNFT MOBILITÄT a dialogue platform for intelligent traffic; Barcelona City Council; Bayerische Akademie der Wissenschaften; BMW Group; Bombardier; Certh; Click&Find; Council for Sustainable transport Denmark; CSIRO; CTAG; DELPHI Deutschland; DENSO Corporation; Deutsches Zentrum fuer Luft-Und Raumfahrt Ev (DLR); Efratios Arampatzis Monoprosopi EPE; Egnatia Motorway SA; Enterprise European Network (EEN); ERTICO; ERTRAC; EURECAT; Eurokleis srl; European Union; European Union Road Federation; F. K. Liotopoulos Kai Sia Ee; Federal State Agency for Intelligent Transport Systems; Federation Internationale de l'Automobile; Florence city council; Forum of European National Highway Research Laboratories; French Authorities; Fujitsu; Hellenic Institute of Transport; Helsinki Transport Authority; Hoyer; Hyundai KIA Motors; Infotrip; Instituto Tecnológico del Embalaje, Transporte y Logística; International Bridge, Tunnel & Turnpike Association (IBTTA); INTIRO AB; ISINNOVA; Italian Ministry of Infrastructures and Transports (Italia ITS Architecture); Italian National Hauliers Association; ITS Australia; ITS Finland; ITS North Rein Westfalia NRW; ITS USA; Kiunsys; KTH; Linköping University; MaaS Alliance; MACOMI; Macomi Bv; Magneti Marelli; Ministry of Infrastructure, Transport and Networks (Greece); Mototres Diseños Industriales SAU; Movalia; Municipality of Patras; Other research institutes; Politecnico di Milano; Port of Melbourne Corporation; Rail Users Ireland; RENAULT; Research Institute of Sweden (RISE); Road and Bridge Research Institute; Robosoft; Roma Servizi Per La Mobilità Srl; SGS; Shenzhen Huaru Technology Co., Ltd.

8.4 Vertex Group 4

Hogia UK (Hogia Transport Systems Ltd); International Road Transport Union (IRU); Tom Tom/TUE; AA Singapore; ABADA; ABBAT; ACCI; ACEA; AEBTRI; AFTRI; AIRCA; AIRCUZ; AIRH; AIRTO-KR; AIST; AITA; AITWA; ALIS; ALSA; AMERIT; AMTRI; ANALTIR; ANAV; ANTRAM; ANTROP; ARTRI; ASMAP; ASMAP UA; ASRTU; Association of Paneuropean Coach Terminals; ASTAG; ASTIC; Asyad; ATA; ATCE; ATCUAE; ATIA; ATTO; BAAV; BAMAP; BDO; BGL; BWVL; BZP; CANACAR; CARCOSERCO; CCIABML; CCIT; CESMAD Bohemia; CESMAD Slovakia; Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia (SCC-ATT); CLC; Colfecar; CONFETRA; CPT; CRTA; CTA; CTU; DB; DI; DKV; DSLV; DTL; DTR; Elgin; ERAA; ESPORG; ESTA; EuroLines; EVO; FADEEAC; FAI; FBAA; FEBETRA; FEDEMAC; FEDETAXI; FIAP; FLEAA; FNTR; FNTV; FT CGEM; FTA; GIRCA; Global Passenger Network (GPN); GOCA; GTL; Hellenic Institute of Transport (H.I.T.); ICB; ICCIMA; INGO group; International Refrigerated Transportation Association; Intertransport; IRHA; IRTB; ITD; ITEO; ITLB; JTA; KATC; KazATO; KCC; KNV; LAL; LATVIJAS AUTO; LINAVA; Michelin; MKFE; Mwasalat; NARTAM; National Association of Telematics for Transport and Safety (TTS Italia); NHO Transport; NLF; NT; NTC; OFAE; OPSTAC; PANTEIA; Peugeot & other manufacturers; PKGC; PNC-ICC; POEIATA; PTV; RACJ; RAR; RHA; RISE; Rosgosstrakh; SA; SATA; SBF; SC&RA